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Abstract

Deliverable 4.3, a report on recommendations for the most suitable contribution model, aims to identify the main public sources of income for the DiSSCo RI: public funding being the bedrock of the ERIC structure.

This report first explains the ERIC funding framework and its legal constraints. On that basis, it proposes rules and a mathematical formula to define the DiSSCo annual membership fees. The formula suggested is flexible and deliverable 4.3 provides a modelling of the results according to the different options available with the formula. In addition, it presents an analysis of the way funding could be distributed among its members in order to implement decentralized services.

To fund a broader service offer, DiSSCo may need funding from other sources such as European and national funds. Eventually, ERICs like DiSSCo can apply for other funding, such as international organisation funding and sponsorship and foundations. This report delivers information on that additional funding.

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Report on recommendations for the most suitable contribution model

DiSSCo Prepare WP 4 – Deliverable 4.3

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Abstract

Deliverable 4.3, a report on recommendations for the most suitable contribution model, aims to identify the main public sources of income for the DiSSCo RI: public funding being the bedrock of the ERIC structure.

This report first explains the ERIC funding framework and its legal constraints. On that basis, it proposes rules and a mathematical formula to define the DiSSCo annual membership fees. The formula suggested is flexible and deliverable 4.3 provides a modelling of the results according to the different options available with the formula. In addition, it presents an analysis of the way funding could be distributed among its members in order to implement decentralized services. To fund a broader service offer, DiSSCo may need funding from other sources such as European and national funds. Eventually, ERICs like DiSSCo can apply for other funding, such as international organisation funding and sponsorship and foundations. This report delivers information on that additional funding.

The DiSSCo ERIC annual membership fee calculation is based on three main indicators: economic power (GDP), annual spending in research and development, and population size. In the context of DiSSCo, these indicators are connected to a fixed baseline fee: 50,000 € in order to guarantee a minimum significant annual contribution from each participating country and avoid contributions that will be more expensive to manage than to benefit from. This baseline is multiplied by contribution factors which propose different ways to weight the different indicators. For instance, GDP could have a greater or lesser impact on the contribution calculation than R&D spending or population size, and so on.

If, in the end, all 27 EU members plus United Kingdom, Iceland, Norway and Switzerland sign DiSSCo ERIC statutes then, based on this calculation, the annual budget would be 4.5 million euros – regardless of the weight allocated to the different factors. It is understood that probably not all the thirty-one countries listed will fund DiSSCo ERIC. The total amount may not be achieved initially.

The first annual contributions will allow the Central Hub to begin its operation and implement its business strategy. Research Infrastructures like DiSSCo rely on diverse sources of funding, like EU funding, and can decide to charge services. In the long run, the Central Hub will also work to engage new members. DiSSCo research infrastructure (RI) impact and actions will evolve proportionally to the funding available.

KEY WORDS

National contributions, ERIC statutes, membership fees, members, observers, inflation, GDP, GERD, population size, EU funding, alternative funding for ERICs

Abbreviations

BBMRI:	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
CETAF:	Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities, Brussels
DG:	Director General
DiSSCo:	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
EC:	European Commission
ERA:	European Research Area
ERIC:	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI:	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure
EU:	European Union
GA:	General Assembly
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
GERD:	Gross Domestic Expenditure on R&D
GNP:	Gross National Product
HICP:	Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices
ICEDIG:	Innovation and consolidation for large scale digitisation of natural heritage
IO:	International Organisation
IT:	Information Technology
Meise BG:	Agentschap Plantentuin Meise
MNHN:	Muséum national d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris
MoU:	Memorandum of Understanding
Naturalis:	Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden
NHM:	National History Museum, London
NN:	National Node
NSC:	Natural Science Collections
OECD:	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RBINS:	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels
RI:	Research Infrastructure
SGN:	Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung, Frankfurt
SLA:	Service Level Agreement
SYNTHEsys+:	Synthesys of Systematic Resources
UN:	United Nations

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CHAPTER 1: introduction to the public funding model for DiSSCo Research Infrastructure

1.1 Main questions raised by the deliverable 4.3

Deliverable 4.3 examines public funding for the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). During the course of the European DiSSCo Prepare programme, the preferred working hypothesis¹ is that the RI will become a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). This implies the commitment of at least three Member States for recurrent funding of the RI. In parallel, the ERIC model is promoted by the European Commission and thanks to this framework, ERICs can benefit from European funding.

Within this context, this deliverable examines several dimensions of public funding for RIs. Chapter 2 presents what the ERIC legal framework means financially. It contains an analysis of ERIC funding schemes and a critical analysis of other ERICs in operation. The same chapter shares recommendations and information on rules that DiSSCo RI should follow once in operation.

Chapter 3 is based on the recommendations gathered within chapter 2. It proposes a model for annual membership fee calculation. It identifies the indicators on which this membership fee could be based and presents a mathematical formula that mixes these indicators.

Chapter 4 simulates the different effects of the formula through several tables and graphs. This allows an examination of the consequences of the different scenarios.

Chapter 5 evaluates the links between DiSSCo member institutions. It is understood that a distributed RI involves one or more Central Hubs, and national and local entities that participate in the implementation of the RI. The question of funding can then extend to examining the economic and financial links between the ERIC and the partners that participate in the RI's activity. This is all the more crucial within a context of constrained budgets for natural science collections.

ERICs are eligible for other types of funding such as European Union (EU) and national funding. Appendices 4 and 5 present the results of a study of the funding from both the European Commission (EC) and from alternative sources that are available and specifically relevant for DiSSCo ERIC. **These appendices also introduce non-EU funding sources** that have been highlighted during the study and that may be relevant for DiSSCo.

¹ Scory S., Paleco C., et al. DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 7.1, "Analysis of the legal entity models and their suitability for achieving DiSSCo objectives"

1.2 Methodology followed by T4.3 team: Bibliography, benchmark, workshops and interviews

The following working results are based on diverse resources. WP4 - the DiSSCo business framework expert group - used bibliographical resources to better understand how ERIC funding works. The team also benchmarked DiSSCo against sixteen ERICs in operation. WP4 specifically reviewed the statutes of these ERICs, as well as the sections dedicated to national contributions. This allowed the team to adjust their calculation based on a realistic approach, by providing the budgetary range that ERICs can rely upon in relation to the number of members in the ERIC. It also gave an overview of typical variables which are used in national contribution models (GDP, GDP/Capita, etc.).

In parallel with this study, the working group met DiSSCo National Node representatives in order to better understand the national landscape and national funding opportunities. This allowed a better understanding of funders' expectations and ways to engage them in the DiSSCo construction process. Representatives from other Research Infrastructures were also invited to share their experiences. Their advice and feedback guided DiSSCo CSO in taking feasible decisions.

Finally, the T4.3 working group has worked with a subcontractor who has expertise in ERICs organisation. Appendix 1 contains a presentation of this company: X Officio

1.3 Definitions of the terms and concepts used

'Associated country' means a third country which is a party to an international agreement with the European Union, under the terms or on the basis of which it makes a financial contribution to all or part of the Community research, technological development and demonstration programmes.

'Construction phase': implementation of national / regional investment plans for infrastructure upgrades and large-scale digitisation programmes; application of joint DiSSCo programmes and policies, quality control and risk management; establishment of regional/ thematic hubs; active membership; construction of the DiSSCo Hub (including all services).

Director General: is the executive level in charge of implementing the decisions of the General Assembly (GA) and is responsible for the execution of the work programme. The Director-General should have the authority to make certain independent decisions within limits set by the GA and to promote the interests of DiSSCo ERIC without seeking advance approval from the GA.

'Distributed Research Infrastructure': is "a network of distributed resources" and consists of a Central Hub (i.e. coordination secretariat) and interlinked National Nodes, which can by extension coordinate local nodes. An important distinction in dependence exists between distributed RIs (which, according to the ESFRI roadmap, need – among other requirements – to be identified by a unique name, legal statutes, and governance structure) and a coordinated research network (which is instead the collaboration of fully independent research performing organisations).

'DiSSCo Stakeholders' are users and organisations which either have an interest, directly or indirectly, in DiSSCo or have some influence on DiSSCo and its services.

'DiSSCo User' means anyone who uses and /or benefits from DiSSCo services.

'DiSSCo Centre of Excellence'(DCE)- a concept that is still under discussion within DPP - meaning an institution, national node, service provider node, regional node or transnational group of institutions, with proven excellence in a given domain, providing a specific service at European level to DiSSCo RI users.

'DiSSCo National Node' is one or more national facilities operating in the same country.

'DiSSCo ERIC': The legal entity and statutory seat of DiSSCo, responsible for overseeing implementation of the Statutes and for all aspects of DiSSCo activities.

'DiSSCo Central Hub': is part of the executive management of the RI managed by the Director-General with the support of a secretariat, in charge of operating the RI.

'DiSSCo facility': the geographically distributed collection-holding organisation(s) (i.e., natural science/history collection(s)) and related third-party organisations that deliver data and expertise to the DiSSCo Hub infrastructure, and which can be accessed by users via the DiSSCo Hub infrastructure.² A DiSSCo facility is present in and represented by a National Node.

'DiSSCo Perimeter': can be represented with concentric circles. At the centre there is a hub which coordinates demand and service provision. Around this hub, there is the ERIC perimeter (first circle): it can encompass other facilities than the hub - in this scenario, Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are signed with institutions who become service providers on behalf of the ERIC. Finally, there is the second circle which is the Research Infrastructure. Inside it are the institutions who preserve Natural Science Collections (NSCs) and provide services and data.

'ERIC member': EU countries and also, under certain conditions, associated countries, other non-EU countries and international organisations, negotiate the content of the statutes of the ERIC and its annexes in accordance with the regulation. To establish an ERIC a minimum number of members is necessary. At least one EU country and 2 other countries, which are either EU countries or associated countries, is the minimum configuration. Other members can join later depending on the conditions specified in the statutes.

'ERIC observer': Next to full membership, Member States should be able to become observers of an ERIC based on the conditions specified in its Statutes.

General Assembly: Is the highest governing body representing the collective interests of the member countries and is the ultimate decision-making body. It will define the strategic direction of the DiSSCo

² Hardisty A. *et al* (2020) Conceptual design blueprint for the DiSSCo digitization infrastructure – Deliverable 8.1, DOI: 10.3897/rio.6.e54280

ERIC and will vote on adoption of the budget. The General Assembly can have several categories of membership, including international organisations, with differing rights and responsibilities.

'Government funding': member contributions; in the case of an ERIC member. Only Member States, associated countries, third countries other than associated countries and intergovernmental organisations can be members of an ERIC.

In-kind: An in-kind contribution is a non-monetary contribution. Goods or services offered for free or for less than the usual charge constitute in-kind contributions. Opposite: cash contribution.

'Operation phase': Full deployment of operations and services; first full evaluation process; review of organisation and business model; full scale operations.

'Research Infrastructure' (RI) means facilities, resources and related services that are used by the scientific community to conduct top-level research in their respective fields and to cover major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives or structures for scientific information; enabling Information and Communications Technology-based infrastructures such as grid, computing, software and communication, or any other entity of a unique nature essential to achieve excellence in research.

'Third country' means a State that is not a Member State of the European Union.

CHAPTER 2: understanding the ERIC framework

2.1 A legal constraint: the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)

The ERIC status created by the European regulation of the 25/06/2009³ is recognised throughout the Union. Awarded by the Commission, it allows privileged access to EU-funded calls for projects, and benefits from VAT exemption in most member countries. It is based on a commitment from at least three countries (including at least one from the EU), over a period of at least three to five years, supported by a business plan and a provisional budget, which is considered as a commitment from the countries concerned.

The ERIC initiative aims to promote and support the development of common research and innovation practices at the European level, through the set-up of Pan-European RI and the creation of the

³ Official Journal of the European Union, Council regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Available on: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009R0723&from=HR>

European Research Area (ERA). The idea is to develop a common strategy and establish priorities for new RIs of Pan-European interest.

ERICs result from a complex interplay between the EU and the Member States, in terms of collaboration, data and resources sharing, and funding. Due to the broad diversity in the missions of ERICs and the variety of access and service provision, there is no one single applicable funding scheme and the needs in terms of funding for projects supported by ERICs are highly variable. Funding mechanisms must therefore be carefully adapted to each ERIC.

The advantages of an ERIC are the following:

- ◆ A legal capacity recognized in all EU countries;
- ◆ Flexibility to adapt to specific requirements of each infrastructure;
- ◆ A faster process than creating an international organization;
- ◆ Exemptions from VAT and excise duty;
- ◆ An ERIC may adopt its own procurement procedures which have to respect the principles of transparency, non-discrimination and competition.

2.2 Financial rules an ERIC should follow

There are no financial rules dedicated solely to ERICs. The ERIC regulation states that an ERIC shall carry out its activities according to sound budgetary principles for the exercise of its financial responsibility.⁴ All items of revenue and expenditure of an ERIC shall be included in estimates to be drawn up for each financial year and shall be shown in the annual budget (where revenues and expenditures shall be in balance). The regulation further notes that principles of sound financial management need to be implemented. The ERIC Practical Guidelines⁵ further include the principle of transparency for establishing and implementing the budget and for presenting the accounts.

⁴ Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), available on: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/GA/TXT/?uri=celex:32009R0723>

⁵ ERIC Practical guidelines – Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, EC (2015). Available on: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c6647f05-874e-4cdd-af70-22ade4759930>

The key elements of an internal rules document on “financial rules” are:

- a. Framework: describe the ERIC in managerial summary;
- b. Financial management principles: repeat those from the ERIC regulation, the Statutes and add others specific to your RI;
- c. Financial year dates;
- d. Currency;
- e. Request and dates for the annual contributions: when shall members pay their contribution, received in one or in several instalments and at which dates;
- f. Interest rate to late contributions: how to deal with countries paying late or not at all;
- g. Detailed formula for the mandatory annual contributions if not described in the statutes;
- h. Rules to calculate membership fee for new members to join during the year: full membership fee or only parts, calculated from the month/quarter/half year;
- i. Reference to statistical sources for the formula ingredients: put in all those references needed for the calculation of the membership share and how you use them;
- j. Host country contribution/premium if not mentioned in the statutes: is it fixed by amount or percentage, how is it amended and/or evaluated;
- k. Value and evaluation rules for in-kind contributions: in case in-kind contributions are available describe the process how they will be estimated or calculated and how they are evaluated and decided if their value will be included in the accounts;
- l. How the draft budget is assembled and approved: who does what in preparing the budget and the contribution;
- m. Accounting principles and rules: do you follow international accounting rules (IFRS) or if national, why;
- n. Financial audits: how is the process of financial audits set up and by whom;
- o. Principles of loans and bank overdrafts: who can draft loans and overdrafts approved by whom;
- p. Financial reporting: what shall be reported to whom and how; for a very good summary refer to the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Guidance document on accounting principles for ERICs;
- q. Duration of record keeping beyond the national rules: what are the national rules, and do you keep them longer?

2.3 Main patterns for the rules governing ERIC national contributions

A benchmarking exercise was carried out in order to study the main variables which impact the national contribution models of 16 ERICs. For WP4 it was a way to identify the main rules to focus on in order to develop a contribution system for DiSSCo. This work was based on the EUR-Lex websites⁶, containing the official versions of ERICs statutes.

The benchmark - a spreadsheet comprising two tabs - includes general information of 16 ERICs; links to their published statutes; domain; starting year; number of members and observers; hosting country; GDP (gross domestic product) per inhabitants of hosting country; OECD price level indices of 2019; number of members during preparatory phase; country of the coordinator during preparatory phase; host country contribution (with amount only for France); national cash contributions in 2019; R&D project volumes; income figures (only some identified); other income; host country cash contribution; host country in kind contribution; other in kind contribution; and total amount. The second tab provides information on the membership of the 16 ERICs, such as the type of membership contribution and the rules regulating it, financial figures, and data sources.

Not all the ERICs studied have the same maturity, as they were created between 2011 and 2018. Nor are they all in the same scientific field as DiSSCo (environment). Some of them belong to social and cultural innovation, others to energy, some to health and food. According to the information collected, the minimum total amount of annual contribution is 220,000 euros per year, and the maximum is 2.2 million euros per year. This information was found via Internet searches, notably through annual reports that are publicly available on the ERIC page of the EC website. Considering that ERIC's annual budgets reports are not always clear, specifically that their income categories do not make the same distinction between the different sources of income, this information might not be 100% accurate.

According to this benchmark, the main rules that exist among ERICs statutes are:

- ◆ A minimum and a maximum fixed annual membership fee;
- ◆ A distinction made between members and observers;
- ◆ A place given to International organisations;
- ◆ Possibility to add a rule for variable funding;
- ◆ A maximum threshold of contribution above which a single member-country cannot provide the equivalent on his own;
- ◆ A fixed rule for Host premium contribution;
- ◆ A distinction between in-kind and cash contributions;
- ◆ A fixed rule to compensate inflation over time;
- ◆ A minimum 5-years commitment;
- ◆ Rule in case of early withdrawal;
- ◆ Rule for non-member/observer users;
- ◆ Rule for late contribution;
- ◆ New member adjusted contributions;
- ◆ Rules for non-EU countries;
- ◆ Cost perimeter covered by the national contributions.

⁶ EUR-Lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html?locale=en>

2.4 Comparison with DiSSCo needs and options

This benchmark on the annual national contributions of Member Countries for 16 ERICs was reviewed by a subcontractor (X-Officio - see appendix 1) with more experience in ERICs. Based on their knowledge of DiSSCo and on national contribution systems for ERICs, they compiled advice for WP4 which has helped in the development of DiSSCo annual national contributions. According to their expertise, the following ERICs' statutes contain components of interest for DiSSCo: BBMRI, EPOS, EU-OPENSREEN and LifeWatch ERIC. Still, there are components from other ERICs which are recommended to include, as shown in the following section.

Table 1 - Overview: ERIC contribution model compatibility with DiSSCo

	National contributions rules - Compatibility with DiSSCo
BBMRI	Compatible
CESSDA	Not compatible
DARIAH	
EATRIS	
ECCSEL	
ECRIN	
EMBRC	
EMSO	
EPOS	
ESS	
EU-OPENSREEN	
EURO-Argo	
ICOS	
INSTRUCT	
LifeWatch	
SHARE	

BBMRI: this model could be used for DiSSCo as **it provides both fixed and variable contributions**. The variable share is based on the GDP of participating countries. Observer contribution is included (variable share is 30% for the GDP). There is a **maximum of 25% for individual countries and international organisations pay a fixed amount**, individually calculated, and fixed by the General Assembly. What is missing from these statutes is the host premium (for BBMRI it is in the internal rules document).

CESSDA: the model **does not contain a fixed share for all members**, but fixed shares for two countries. The calculation method is not published. The other participating countries pay a share based on GDP, but again the mathematical formula is not provided. This case does not fit DiSSCO's purpose as it reflects a very specific ERIC with two main partners and no calculation method is provided.

DARIAH: their calculation model combines relative size of GDP (divided by the sum of the GDP of the Council of Europe member states) with cash and in-kind contributions. Details of the formula are not provided. **Because of the calculation base and the lack of details provided, this model is not**

recommended for use by DiSSCo. What is interesting is (1) an **automatic increase of 2% per year of the national annual contribution to compensate for inflation**, and (2) a **monthly calculated fee for new members joining**.

EATRIS: this model consists of **both a fixed, as well as a variable share**. The fixed share also distinguishes based on population size (fewer or more than 7.5m people). The variable share is also a fixed amount distinguished by the amount of national R&D expenditure per country (5k for <4bn, 25k for 4-12bn, and 40k for >12bn). It is not clear how these thresholds are chosen and furthermore they are overruled by minimum and maximum overall thresholds of 50k to 140k Euros. **Because of the lack of transparency of the chosen thresholds, in addition to the lack of inclusion of economic power (GDP) of a country, we cannot recommend this method for DiSSCo.** What remains of interest, however, is a rule ensuring compensation in case of withdrawal of bigger countries (>7% of total contribution).

ECCSEL: this model is not of use to DiSSCo as it contains a 1/3 share of the hosting country and equal amounts (not exceeding 80k) for participating countries - not distinguishing size, economic power, etc.

ECRIN: the ECRIN model does not fulfil DiSSCo's needs as it comprises contributions of individual contact persons in the countries, plus a fixed amount by GDP (20k for GDP<200 bn; 100k for GDP between 200-1000 bn; and 250k for GDP>1000 bn); **but it includes the host country premium and a rule for joining national contributions to compensate for 50% of existing national contributions.**

EMBRC: annual contributions are calculated based on a mixed flat-rate/GDP-based/GDP per capita-based model with different weights and a published formula. The host country contribution is included. **The formula used for this model is somewhat complicated**, and the reasons why the different weights have been chosen are not clear. As a result, annual contributions will change year-on-year. We believe this should not be recommended for DiSSCo.

EMSO: EMSO's model is **explained as having fixed amounts per member and hosting country, regardless of the size of the country, its economic capacity, or other components.** Therefore, this model cannot be recommended for DiSSCo.

EPOS: the statutes of EPOS ERIC contain a **detailed formula** on how to calculate the membership fee. **The contribution is 50% equally fixed and 50% according to GDP contribution.** The minimum contribution is 50k per annum. In principle this model could be recommended for DiSSCo, excluding the rule of voting rights in proportion to fees.

ESS: the ESS contribution model is not of use to DiSSCo as it is set up as a fixed amount for the ERIC which is only adjusted for inflation. The individual contributions are then calculated based on GDP but with a minimum threshold of 20K. Interestingly, the host country premium is extremely high (about 1/3) of the total national contributions.

EU-OPENSREEN: this contribution model combines equal **fixed amounts for all member countries (25%) and a variable share of 75% according to GDP per capita** (different for member, observer, and host countries). The model includes a limit of **50% of total contributions maximum for an individual member**. In principle a model like this would be useful for DiSSCo.

EURO-Argo ERIC: due to a lack of detail in the statutes, it is not possible to evaluate this model.

ICOS: Alongside the headquarter (HQ), ICOS have institutions hosting additional services and measuring spots. **50% of the contribution is shared equally and 50% is GDP-based**, with additional hosting components. Due to its nature, this model will not be of interest to DiSSCo.

INSTRUCT: this RI has chosen to use a **3-block system based on the number of researchers in science and technology per total national population with cash contributions of 50k, 75k and 100k**. Unfortunately, this model with general research staff **does not reflect the relative manpower of a certain field**. It also neglects to consider the overall economic power of a country. Therefore, this model is not recommended for DiSSCo.

LifeWatch: Lifewatch ERIC has implemented a GDP-dependent linear based contribution model, **with a minimum and maximum threshold**. Unfortunately, the statutes do not show these thresholds in detail. This constitutes the **simplest model for calculating mandatory annual contributions** and therefore it is a possible model for DiSSCo. Interestingly, LifeWatch's budgets are always fixed for 5 years.

SHARE: much like ESS-ERIC, the SHARE contribution model is based on the principle that the host country covers HQ resources, and the member contribution covers the national surveys. This is a very different model to what is envisaged for DiSSCo, and is therefore not recommended.

2.5. Main recommendations for DiSSCo national membership fee calculation

There is no classic model which ERICs can copy and paste or which all countries have agreed on. Therefore, each ERIC needs to develop its own specific model, adjusted to its specificities, and needs.

Contribution models are typically intended to meet the following objectives:

1. The different countries' shares should be calculated according to a transparent methodology relevant to the purpose of the ERIC, such as their population size, economic power, number of potential users, R&D spending, or shall be equal for all.
2. The method chosen shall be based on transparent, easy-to-acquire statistics and should make comparisons between countries possible.
3. Can have minimum and maximum thresholds in numbers as well as a maximum % for each individual country.
4. Include a specific rule or % for the host country premium.
5. May include an automatic adjustment for inflation.
6. Could foresee a specific fee for countries withdrawing early.
7. Include an adjusted formula for countries joining mid-year.
8. Special clauses for high volume infrastructure/equipment (not relevant of interest for DiSSCo).

- **Population size** is a good first indication in approaching comparability, as it is easy to identify for most countries. It does not however reflect the economic power of a country nor its R&D capacity.
- **Economic power** is typically represented by **Gross Domestic Product (GDP)** or **Gross National Product (GNP)**. Both represent the total market value of all goods and services produced over a certain period. However, they are calculated in slightly different ways. GDP is the value of the finished domestic goods and services produced within a nation's borders. On the other hand, GNP is the value of all finished goods and services owned by a country's citizens, whether those goods are produced in that country or not. While GDP limits its interpretation of the economy to the geographical borders of the country, GNP extends it to include the net overseas economic activities performed by its nationals. **GDP is more often used**, sometimes called GNI (Gross National Income). As countries might expect annual differences in GDP, some ERICs prefer to calculate the average GDP over a number of years (typically 3 years).
- **Research and Development (R&D)**: When it comes to using **R&D figures, one must distinguish between (1) gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD), (2) R&D expenditure by sector of performance, and (3) R&D expenditure by source of funds**. All these figures are available for EU and OECD countries. **GERD** includes expenditure on research and development by business enterprises, higher education institutions, as well as government and private non-profit organisations. In order to make the figures more comparable, GERD is often expressed relative to GDP or in relation to population. **The ratio of GERD to GDP** is also known as R&D intensity. As most R&D expenditure is covered by industry, and different countries have a different industrial base, countries might not be comparable. Alternatively, one might look at the higher education sector, or private non-profit sector. Finally, one might wish to use **R&D expenditure by source of funds**. R&D expenditure by sources of funds describes the origin of the R&D funding for a statistical unit.⁷ Performer-based reporting of the sums which one unit, organisation, or sector has received from another unit, organisation, or sector for the performance of intramural R&D. R&D funds are identified with two criteria: there must be a direct transfer of resources and this transfer must be both intended and used for the performance of R&D. Source-based reporting of extramural expenditures which are the amounts a unit, an organisation, or a sector reports having paid to another unit, organisation, or sector for the performance of R&D.
- **Number of users per country**: Very often institutions would like to use **the number of potential users of a country or, if that is not available, the number of researchers**. R&D personnel consists of all individuals employed directly in the field of R&D, including persons providing direct services, such as managers, administrators, and clerical staff. R&D researchers can be employed in the public or the private sector - including academia - to create new knowledge, products, processes, and methods, as well as to manage the projects concerned. Countries with a stronger industrial base therefore might have a higher number of R&D staff, making it more difficult to estimate potential users of a RI, who currently (with exceptions) mainly come from academia or the public sector.

⁷ All definitions are derived from both EUROSTAT and OECD statistics

For most countries, reliable past and current statistics **are available from EUROSTAT, OECD.Stat and or World Bank Open Data.**

- **Introduce a threshold:** as some EU countries can be very small (e.g. Luxembourg) or very big (e.g. Germany), consortia developing a contribution model want to implement thresholds to ensure fairness. This might make sense when the formula developed is only based on population size or economic power alone. In such a case one would either introduce absolute or relative thresholds. Examples are minimum and/or maximum amounts or percentages. Another possibility is to split the contribution into fixed and variable amounts. In the latter case, there might still be a difference in size (e.g. in the case of BBMRI or EATRIS) or a fixed amount (e.g. in EU-OPENSREEN). To reduce the risk of larger countries having to pay almost all of the total member contributions, some ERICs have introduced a mechanism of maximum share (BBMRI and EU-OPENSREEN), with a redistribution of the overpayment across other participants.
- **Host country premium:** The host country premium or the additional contribution of the state of incorporation (Statutory seat) is a delicate matter. Comparisons show a very diverse picture with no common rule. The minimal amount should be able to cover the expenses for the central office (without the personnel), incorporation, insurance, taxes etc. In rare cases several countries pay a premium for hosting specific common services (e.g. ICOS and BBMRI); this premium should be calculated transparently. Ultimately, it will depend on negotiation with the potential host country(ies).
- **Inflation rate:** Nowadays, as inflation rates can be quite high, it is **recommended to include a consideration of inflation in the calculation**. Inflation is the increase in the general level of prices of goods and services in an economy; the reverse situation is deflation, when prices decrease across the board. Inflation and deflation are usually measured by consumer price indices or retail price indices. Within the EU, a specific consumer price index has been developed: the harmonised index of consumer prices (HICP). One possibility is either a fixed or a flexible percentage, calculated based on the previous year's figures. It would therefore be a case of choosing the flexible percentage or using the index relevant for the host country (as most goods and services would be covered there) or an average of participating states (which will need to be recalculated with each new member), or the EU average.
- **Withdrawal of member countries:** withdrawal of member countries will always represent an important change, as the money might have already been allocated, or personnel hired. Therefore, reasonable measures need to be taken to notify in advance (1-2 years ahead of withdrawal for less equipment-based RIs and 5-10 years for heavily equipment-based RIs) and/or foreseen fees (e.g. in percentage of the annual contribution) for premature departure (25-30% per annum). An interesting additional example provided by EATRIS is the rule for compensation in case of withdrawal of bigger countries (representing a loss of more than 7% of total contributions) by shifting those funds to the other participating countries.

2.6 Additional information on ERIC contribution models

1. *Embedding international organisations*

ERICs allow international organisations (IO), for example the United Nations (UN), to be members or observers. In the case of the UN, it requires the permission of the 193 members. For embedding IO as observers, the Director General (DG) can simply decide and there is no hard and fast rule as to how to calculate their contribution. It can be directly negotiated between the IO and the ERIC's GA. It is not mandatory that it is specified in the statutes. For instance, it can be decided during the first GA.

2. *Minimum number of members to guarantee the funding of the RI*

No rule needs to be written in the statutes in order to guarantee a minimum level of funding for the ERIC. If some members leave the RI over the course of its implementation, it is possible to raise the topic during the GA and see if national contributions should be increased, or the level of service provided decreased.

Based on advice from X-Officio (See appendix 1), by experience, **it is not recommended to launch the ERIC with fewer than 5 countries.**

In case of a withdrawal of a member during the first 5 years of operation, the country concerned will have to pay for all 5 years of their initial commitment. This rule is guaranteed by the ERIC regulation. If a member does not want to pay, the ERIC would have the right to take them to court. In case of a withdrawal of a member after this 5-year period, the GA should be notified at least 2-3 years in advance: this clause should be included in the Statutes.

3. *Minimum contributions expected from observers*

There is no rule for the minimum contribution expected from observers, although the details of observers' subscription to the ERIC should be detailed in the ERIC's statutes. It is realistic to ask 1/4 to 1/3 of the full membership fee, which is the typical observer's fee for several ERICs. If observers have the same rights to access the services than members, 1/3 of the regular member contribution amount may be appropriate.

4. *Definition of in-kind: statutes or service level agreements (SLAs)*

This depends on the expectations from the ERIC towards its member-institutions. If the in-kind contribution is strategically important, it is possible to write in the statutes that there will be an expectation on the participating institutions to contribute in-kind. It is also possible to add in the introduction of the ERIC statutes that institutions will be asked to contribute in-kind.

Regarding the amount of the expected in-kind contribution, this is to be included in the service level agreements (SLAs). In the annexes, it is possible to foresee the annual agreed monetary equivalent on which the annual commitment is defined.

5. *General Assembly and voting of the budget*

Budgetary cycles should not be specifically mentioned in the Statutes. Each year the budget is drafted and, as long as the GA agrees with the proposal, it will be actioned. In the case of higher investments (around 1/3 of the regular member contribution amount can be a threshold), it is possible to prepare a two-to-three-year budget with details and share it with the GA.

6. States joining during the year

A rule should be included in the statutes in order to clarify how it would work in case a country joins the ERIC outside of the traditional budgetary cycle. There are two options:

- The country has to pay from the month it joins the ERIC to the end of the year;
- If the country joins the ERIC before the mid-year, it shall pay the full annual membership fee, if it joins the ERIC after the mid-year, it shall pay 50% of the annual membership fee.

In both cases, countries commit to funding the ERIC for 5 years as of its joining.

Joining is not effective as of the date chosen by the member country, but is instead actioned as of the date after the GA has agreed to it, in writing. It is very likely that the decision to welcome a new country will be taken during the GA.

7. Financial penalty in case of early withdrawal

It is not relevant to mention a financial penalty in the statutes in case of early withdrawal of a member country. There is already a rule in place in case a member country withdraws from the ERIC before the end of the first 5 years. A good option is to negotiate early notification in case of a decision to exit the ERIC.

8. Non-EU countries

Non-EU countries can be assigned to the same membership fee calculation. Sometimes, EUROSTAT only holds data for EU countries. In that case, it is possible to use equivalent data from the world bank or OECD.

9. Explanation of the expenditure covered by the national contributions

There is no need to explain what the contributions will cover in the statutes. This will be specified in the annual work programme included with the annual budget. Both documents shall be approved by the GA.

10. ERICs' eligibility to access loans

ERICs can access loans like any private company. In practice, this requires the ERIC to demonstrate its bankability for a lender. The GA is responsible for approving the loan request.

As it currently stands, the only case of an ERIC requesting a loan concerns the European Spallation Source ERIC (ESS). The whole construction cost amounts to 2 billion euros and required a loan guaranteed by the European Investment Bank. This is a very special case and it concerns a huge investment.

In the case of DiSSCo, the decision should be taken 10 years before the request for the loan.

11. In case of reserves / cashflow

Reserve authorisation will depend on the financial and monetary rules of the country with statutory seats. The rules will vary from one country to another. In some countries, ERICs are seen as a private organisation and should therefore follow private financial rules. In other countries, they are seen as public institutions. Typically, in the EU, public organisations are advised against establishing and keeping cash reserves. This caution does not apply to the private sector.

CHAPTER 3: DiSSCo national contributions calculation

3.1 Introduction to DiSSCo Timeline

DiSSCo’s initial developments implemented through EU-funded projects (ICEDIG, MOBILISE COST, DiSSCo Prepare and SYNTHESYS+) already represent an estimated budget of more than €M 13. This budget mainly includes EU funding as well as in-kind contributions from participating institutions. In February 2023, DiSSCo will stop benefitting from these European funding programmes and enter into its transition phase (see figure 1). During the transition period, DiSSCo ERIC’s statutes and national annual contributions will be discussed among its future Members and Observers. The national contributions will represent the fixed annual budget of the RI. It is the funding on which many of the expenditures presented within this document will rely.

The national contributions described within this document are intended to cover core DiSSCo activity for five years: the fixed costs of managing the DiSSCo Central Hub (€M 1.4 per year)⁸ and provision of core services. This assumption is based on an incremental and realistic approach. DiSSCo will first deploy a team with tools to ease access to NSC, who shall help the institutions to follow European shared innovations.

Figure 1 - DiSSCo RI Timeline

⁸ Landel, S.; Casino, A.; Guiraud, M. (2023) The Cost Book for DiSSCo. DiSSCo Prepare WP4 - D4.1.

3.2 Main principles and rules for DiSSCo annual membership fees

Four principles underlie the methodology developed by DiSSCo in order to calculate annual membership:

1. National membership fees shall be fair and equitable. They shall reflect the resources devoted to science and technology among DiSSCo members and countries' population size. Annual spending on R&D and population size should have an impact on the membership fees.
2. The national annual wealth creation shall be an indicator for the DiSSCo annual membership fee. It can be an average of the GDP of the three years preceding the budget year concerned.
3. There should always be a significant minimum financial contribution, regardless of the size of the economy, in order to guarantee a minimum annual contribution from each participating country and avoid contributions that will be more expensive to manage than to benefit from.
4. The DiSSCo RI shall be able to annually adjust the contributions, notably in relation to inflation, and keep a minimum level of services thanks to membership fees, under the first 5 years commitment (see section 2.5).

These principles are supported by the five following recommended rules:

Host Country annual membership: 25% of the annual cost of the Central Hub Office.

Observer: observers shall pay one third of full annual membership, based on the same factors as for members. This is currently being discussed with the national nodes. At this stage it is a working hypothesis.

In-kind: in-kind will be part of the negotiation with funders. The core Cost Book relies on annual cash contributions to fund the central DiSSCo infrastructure and management. It is understood that the wider RI relies on its member institutions' in-kind contributions.

New member, new observer: if a new member/observer joins before the mid-year (2 July), they shall pay the full annual fee. If they join the ERIC after the mid-year, they shall pay half of the annual fee.

Limit maximum impact from one country: one Member State annual contribution shall not exceed 50% of total annual contributions to DiSSCo ERIC.

3.3 Relevant indicators for DiSSCo: economic power, R&D spending and population size

When it comes to national annual contributions to research infrastructures, their calculation should strive to fairly distribute financial commitment among its members. As DiSSCo is implemented within the EU landscape, a useful source of indicators is the EUROSTAT website. In the case where EUROSTAT data are not available, OECD data or the World Bank data can be used instead.

Two possible options on which to base the DiSSCo ERIC formula to calculate the membership fee have been defined. Both consider the GDP, R&D spending and population size of potential DiSSCo Member States. Countries do not rank identically if gross or per capita values are considered. As a consequence, mixing gross and per capita in the formula lessens the difference. Furthermore, countries rank differently with respect to GDP and GERD. Therefore, mixing GERD and GDP in the formula contributes also to averaging these differences. Hence, two options:

- The first option mixes Gross Domestic Product (GPD) and Gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) per capita. The GDP is the value of the finished domestic goods and services produced within a nation's borders. GERD per capita is the expenditure on research and development by business enterprises, higher education institutions, as well as government and private non-profit organisations, divided by the number of people living in the country.
- The second option mixes GDP per capita and GERD. GDP per capita is the total value of all the goods and services produced by a country in a particular year, divided by the number of people living there. GERD is the expenditure on research and development by business enterprises, higher education institutions, as well as government and private non-profit organisations.

As part of this calculation, it is understood that some countries could have annual differences in GDP. In order to streamline that figure, DiSSCo ERIC national contributions can be calculated on the average GDP and GERD over 3 years (see appendix 3).

The indicators preselected, GERD/cap, GDP, GERD, GDP/cap, do not vary widely over time. Whilst they did grow between 2017 and 2019, no drastic variation was identified. One conclusion is that they are sustainable and are unlikely to demonstrate significant variation with time. This means that funding connected to these variables should be stable.

The size of the Natural Science collections (NSCs) of the participating countries was not selected as an indicator. The figures on the collections are provided by institutions, it means by the ERIC potential members and service providers. Meanwhile, the contribution model requires indicators that come from external stakeholders. Population size, GDP, R&D expenditure, (etc.) figures are provided by EUROSTAT, World Bank, OECD. These figures are more robust and out of conflict of interest. At the same time, for some institutions the figures on the size of collections still need to be clarified.

3.4 DiSSCo annual membership (DAM) fee formula

The baseline (defined as F) is set at 50,000 € per year, which corresponds to the minimum annual contribution from each Member States. This means that each DiSSCo Member State should pay at least that amount of money to be a member of DiSSCo ERIC.

In order to scale national contributions based on the country's (x) annual GDP, GERD and population size (/cap), different criteria (Cri) are determined. The criteria allow us to rank the countries from 1 to

10. For instance, the country with the lowest GDP is ranked at 1, and the country with the highest GDP is ranked at 10. This is done for every indicator listed.

With these criteria, two options are on the table:

- **The first option combines the GDP and R&D/cap criteria.** It leads to a contribution factor (A) calculated for each potential member. This contribution factor adds up both criteria and allows us to weigh the importance of each criterium in the calculation. With that option it is possible to say that GDP criterion is more important than R&D/cap based on a determined percentage (for instance 75% GDP - 25% R&D/cap).
- **The second option combines GDP/cap and R&D criteria.** It works exactly the same way as for the second option: both criteria can be weighed in the formula.

For every country (x) wishing to become a Member State, the annual membership fee is equal to the baseline (F = 50,000 €) multiplied by the contribution factor linked to the country. For each observer, the baseline is one third of the annual membership. In addition, the host premium contribution (H) is calculated in relation to an estimation of the Central Hub costs and it should cover 25% of the estimated budget.

DiSSCo general membership fee calculation model

For members:

$$DAM(x) = F * A(x)$$

For Host premium:

$$DAM(x) = F * A(x) + H$$

For observers:

$$DAM(x) = (1/3) * [F * A(x)]$$

DAM: DiSSCo annual membership

F: baseline fee = 50,000 €

I: indicators = GDP, GDP/cap, R&D, R&D/cap

Cri: $[(10-1)/(maxI-minI)] * I(x) + [10 - ((10-1)/(maxI-minI))] * I(x)$

A: Contribution factor = $CFa = (1-\alpha) * CriGDP + \alpha CriR\&D/cap$ or $CFa = (1-\alpha) * CriGDP + \alpha CriR\&D$
With α ranging 0 - 100%

x: country

H: Host premium fee calculation (25% of Central Hub Office annual costs)

According to the formula presented above, different options were tested: tests were done with different distributions (25% GERD/cap - 75% GDP; 80% GERD - 20% GDP/cap; etc.). The total sum of all contributions was never exactly the same. In order to be comparable and to avoid a discussion on the total amount of contributions, it was proposed that the addition of all contributions should always be equal to 4,500,000 euros. This amount represents the median of all the different results calculated and it means that whatever percentages are chosen, the total result will always be around €M 4.5. It is understood that probably not all potential countries will sign the ERIC so this total amount will most likely not be achieved, at least not during the first few years of implementation.

CHAPTER 4: modelling the effects of the flexible DiSSCo national contribution formula

As we understand that the DiSSCo national contribution model is flexible and can be negotiated, the working group tested the different options opened for Funders in order to see what would be the effects of the mix of the different indicators. As mentioned in section 3.3, there was a list of four criteria:

- Gross domestic product (GDP)
- Gross domestic product per capita (GDP/cap)
- Gross expenditure on Research and Development (GERD)
- Gross expenditure on Research and Development per capita (GERD/cap)

It leads to three different options:

- GDP and GERD
- GDP and GERD/cap
- GDP/cap and GERD

This chapter aims to model what would be the effects of these different options on the DiSSCo annual membership fees. In addition, it will take the hypothesis of the Funders Forum eleven members and verify the scenario under which all of them would sign the DiSSCo ERIC statutes and would annually contribute to the Research infrastructure funding. The model will simulate the total annual budget of the RI with this scenario. Finally, this chapter will simulate the effects of inflation on the medium term of these contributions.

4.1 Option A: GDP and GERD

The first option excludes the population size (per cap) as a factor and only considers GDP and GERD. With that option, it is possible to weight both criteria differently. Within WP4, a series of 10 options were tested.

Serie A	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%

1	Austria
2	Belgium
3	Bulgaria
4	Croatia
5	Cyprus
6	Czechia
7	Denmark
8	Estonia
9	Finland
10	France
11	Germany
12	Greece
13	Hungary
14	Iceland
15	Ireland
16	Italy
17	Latvia
18	Lithuania
19	Luxembourg
20	Malta
21	Netherlands
22	Norway
23	Poland
24	Portugal
25	Romania
26	Slovakia
27	Slovenia
28	Spain
29	Sweden
30	Switzerland
31	United Kingdom

Figure 2 - Option A, GDP and GERD testing

Ordinate axis: annual contribution per country // Abscissa: countries (numbers correspond to the table on the left side)

With figure 2, it is possible to see that option A is not very well balanced as most of the funding comes from four main countries: Germany, France, Italy and the United Kingdom. It is possible to extract the following data from this testing model:

Table 2: Main data issued from model A, mix of GDP and GERD

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
Standard deviation €	131 722	131 240	130 756	130 415	130 200	130 136	130 232	130 480	130 837	131 565
Min €	61 000	62 000	63 000	64 000	65 000	67 000	68 000	69 000	71 000	72 000
Max €	607 000	618 000	629 000	641 000	653 000	666 000	679 000	693 000	707 000	722 000
Factor	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

With these key data, a high standard deviation is observed and it does not vary from a series to another. One understanding is that this model is not balanced and that annual contributions are not equally distributed among the members.

This option A also shows high minimum contributions (from 60 to 70K EUR/year) and high maximum contributions (from €K 600 to 700 per year). This option may not match with the proposed rule that one country cannot cover more than 50% of the total annual contributions (Section 3.2). In addition, there is a factor of 10 between the minimum annual contribution and the maximum annual contribution. This factor is high in comparison with the other options.

If we test this option with the 11 members of the Funders Forum (Table 3), we see that the research infrastructure would get an annual budget that would cover its annual spending (minimum of €M 1.4 per year).

Table 3: Estimation (in K euros) of annual contributions from Funders Forum members with option A

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Belgium	133	135	137	140	142	144	147	149	152	155
Bulgaria	67	68	69	69	70	71	72	73	74	75
Denmark	108	109	111	113	115	118	120	122	125	127
Estonia	63	64	65	66	67	69	70	71	73	74
France	432	429	425	421	417	413	409	404	399	394
Greece	86	86	86	86	86	86	86	86	85	85
Italy	331	321	311	300	289	278	266	254	241	228
Netherlands	181	181	180	180	179	178	178	177	177	176
Portugal	90	90	90	90	90	90	89	89	89	89
Slovakia	72	73	73	74	74	74	75	75	76	77
United Kingdom	437	427	417	406	395	384	372	359	346	333
Total estimated	2 000	1 983	1 964	1 945	1 924	1 905	1 884	1 859	1 837	1 813
Total with Host premium	2 350	2 333	2 314	2 295	2 274	2 255	2 234	2 209	2 187	2 163

4.2 Option B: GDP and GERD/cap

The second option includes the population criteria and mixes two indicators: GDP and GERD/cap. As the formula remains the same, it is possible to weight the different indicators, as it is shown in the following table:

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD/cap	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%

Figure 3- Model with GDP and GERD/cap

1	Austria
2	Belgium
3	Bulgaria
4	Croatia
5	Cyprus
6	Czechia
7	Denmark
8	Estonia
9	Finland
10	France
11	Germany
12	Greece
13	Hungary
14	Iceland
15	Ireland
16	Italy
17	Latvia
18	Lithuania
19	Luxembourg
20	Malta
21	Netherlands
22	Norway
23	Poland
24	Portugal
25	Romania
26	Slovakia
27	Slovenia
28	Spain
29	Sweden
30	Switzerland
31	United Kingdom

Ordinate axis: annual contribution per country // Abscissa: countries (numbers correspond to the table on the left side)

With figure 3 we see that when we mix GDP and GERD/cap, the results are a bit more distributed among the members, compared to Option A (Figure 2). Some countries with high GERD/cap can contribute more and the annual contribution can be more broadly distributed. Such an assumption is confirmed thanks to the following data:

Table 4: Main data issued from model B, mix of GDP and GERD/cap

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD/cap	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
Standard deviation €	117 716	106 048	97 204	91 030	87 719	86 815	87 833	90 577	94 450	99 058
Min €	59 000	58 000	57 000	55 000	53 000	51 000	49 000	47 000	45 000	42 000
Max €	547 000	502 000	461 000	422 000	387 000	353 000	356 000	377 000	397 000	415 000
Factor	9	9	8	8	7	7	7	8	9	10

This table with the calculated data allows us to observe that the standard deviation varies more: from €K 120 to €K 86. The option with the smallest standard deviation mixes 40% GDP and 60% GERD/cap. Such an option allows for a minimum contribution of €K 51K per year and a maximum of €K 353 per year. There is a factor of 7 between the minimum and the maximum contributions, which is more balanced than for Option A.

If we test this option with the eleven countries that are members of the DiSSCo Funders Forum, once again we see that whatever are the percentages chosen, the RI would get enough budget to cover its annual expenditure.

Table 5: Estimation of annual contributions (in K euros) from Funders Forum members with option B

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Belgium	144	156	167	177	187	196	204	212	219	226
Bulgaria	63	60	58	55	53	51	49	47	45	43
Denmark	131	153	174	194	212	229	245	259	273	286
Estonia	64	66	68	70	72	74	75	77	78	80
France	398	363	331	301	273	248	224	201	180	160
Greece	84	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	68	66
Italy	307	277	249	223	199	177	156	137	118	101
Netherlands	183	185	186	187	189	190	191	192	193	193
Portugal	89	87	85	84	83	81	80	79	78	77
Slovakia	70	68	66	64	62	61	60	58	57	56
United Kingdom	404	365	329	295	264	235	208	183	159	137
Total estimated	1 937	1 861	1 792	1 727	1 669	1 615	1 563	1 514	1 468	1 425
Total with Host premium	2 287	2 211	2 142	2 077	2 019	1 965	1 913	1 864	1 818	1 775

4.3 Option C: with GDP/cap and GERD

The third option also includes population size as an indicator and mixes GDP/cap and GERD. As the formula remains the same, it is possible to weight the different indicators, as it is shown in the following table:

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP/cap	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%

Figure 4 - Test Option C: GDP/cap and GERD

Ordinate axis: annual contribution per country // Abscissa: countries (numbers correspond to the table on the left side)

1	Austria
2	Belgium
3	Bulgaria
4	Croatia
5	Cyprus
6	Czechia
7	Denmark
8	Estonia
9	Finland
10	France
11	Germany
12	Greece
13	Hungary
14	Iceland
15	Ireland
16	Italy
17	Latvia
18	Lithuania
19	Luxembourg
20	Malta
21	Netherlands
22	Norway
23	Poland
24	Portugal
25	Romania
26	Slovakia
27	Slovenia
28	Spain
29	Sweden
30	Switzerland
31	United Kingdom

Figure 4 shows that the results with option C are more homogeneously distributed than for options A & B. Only Germany can reach a high point in terms of annual contributions but according to the mix selected it is possible to find a more balanced option. The following data can help to find a more balanced model:

Table 6: Main data issued from model C, mix of GDP/cap and GERD

Serie	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GDP/cap	90%	80%	70%	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
GERD	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
Standard deviation €	84 551	81 455	79 152	78 106	79 068	82 412	88 857	98 949	113 068	131 565
Min €	42 000	44 000	47 000	50 000	53 000	56 000	60 000	64 000	69 000	72 000
Max €	384 000	363 000	340 000	320 000	368 000	422 000	483 000	552 000	631 000	722 000
Factor	9	8	7	6	7	8	8	9	9	10

Table 6 shows that the standard deviation varies from one option to another: from €K 78 to €K 131. Here, the smallest standard deviation is the option which mixes 60% of GDP/cap and 40% GERD. It is the option where all national contributions are the least scattered around the median. With that option, the minimum annual contribution is €K 50 per year and the maximum is €K 320 per year. There is a factor of 6 between the minimum and the maximum: it allows for a more balanced national contributions model.

This model also goes through the test with the 11 funders forum members. If we add all of their annual contributions, the total covers the expenditure of the research infrastructure and allows for its implementation.

Table 7: Estimation (in K euros) of annual contributions from Funders Forum members with option C

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Belgium	168	168	166	165	164	163	161	159	157	155
Bulgaria	42	44	47	50	53	56	60	64	69	75
Denmark	211	206	199	192	185	176	166	155	142	127
Estonia	81	81	80	80	79	78	77	77	75	74
France	163	178	196	215	236	260	287	318	354	394
Greece	76	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	84	85
Italy	132	138	146	154	162	172	184	196	211	228
Netherlands	187	186	185	185	184	182	181	180	178	176
Portugal	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	89	89	89
Slovakia	74	74	74	75	75	75	75	76	76	77
United Kingdom	165	176	189	203	218	236	255	278	303	333
Total estimated	1 387	1 415	1 447	1 485	1 523	1 566	1 615	1 674	1 738	1 813
Total with Host premium	1 737	1 765	1 797	1 835	1 873	1 916	1 965	2 024	2 088	2 163

4.4 Hypothesis of contributions adjusted according to inflation

One of the principles of the DiSSCo annual contribution models adds inflation as a factor of evolution of the membership fees. Here, it is understood that this may not be indexed on an annual basis but that every five years (minimum length of commitment), the contributions could evolve according to inflation.

One uncertainty with inflation is that it is highly unpredictable. One option is to understand that according to macroeconomic good practices, it should be around 2% per year. As the working hypothesis is that DiSSCo's statutory seat will be in the Netherlands, the applicable inflation rate is associated with the one of the Netherlands. If the costs of the RI rise due to inflation, it will mainly be connected to the inflation rate of the host country. On that basis, it is possible to model the impact of inflation on DiSSCo's income, as shown on the graph below.

Figure 5: Simulating inflation, between 2024 and 2040 – Basic number: 2% inflation per year

In relation with inflation, three main figures would evolve accordingly:

- The baseline fee (50,000 €)
- The total maximum amount with the addition of the 31 hypothetical members (4,500,000 €)
- The annual host premium fee (350,000 €)

If the RI is launched in 2024, the first indexation of its fees would then be in 2029. According to the data connected to the graph above, the following evolution may happen:

- Indexed baseline fee: 55 200 €
- Indexed total maximum amount: 4 970 000 €
- Annual host premium fee: 390 000 €

If we take the median of annual contributions in 2024 (starting year), and the median of annual contributions in 2029 (+ 5 years), we obtain the graphs below (Figures 6, 7 and 9). We see that in comparison with the total annual contribution, inflation has not a major impact on the evolution of each country's annual membership fees. On average, the contributions would be increased by 10% between 2024 and 2029.

Figure 6: simulation of inflation, Model A

Figure 7: simulation of inflation, Model B

Figure 8: Simulation of inflation, Model C

4.5 Proposal of two most balanced options

As shown in the sections 4.2 and 4.3, the two best balanced options are

- Option B: 40% GDP and 60% GERD/cap
- Option C: 60% GDP/cap and 40% GERD

We recommend these 2 options to share with DiSSCo potential future funders, summarized in Table 8. As a lot of data can be extracted from this flexible formula, a selection has to be made on the basis of predefined criteria.

Table 8: 2024 Annual membership fees (in euros) according to the two recommended options

Countries	Option B - GDP & GERD/cap	Option C – GDP/cap & GERD
Austria	211 000	172 000
Belgium	196 000	165 000
Bulgaria	51 000	50 000
Croatia	57 000	64 000
Cyprus	59 000	98 000
Czechia	93 000	90 000
Denmark	229 000	192 000
Estonia	74 000	80 000
Finland	184 000	159 000
France	248 000	215 000
Germany	353 000	320 000
Greece	73 000	78 000
Hungary	70 000	69 000
Iceland	194 000	209 000
Ireland	149 000	228 000
Italy	177 000	154 000
Latvia	52 000	69 000
Lithuania	60 000	73 000
Luxembourg	178 000	314 000
Malta	59 000	103 000
Netherlands	190 000	185 000
Norway	220 000	236 000
Poland	84 000	73 000
Portugal	81 000	88 000
Romania	57 000	58 000
Slovakia	61 000	75 000
Slovenia	92 000	91 000
Spain	137 000	125 000
Sweden	242 000	189 000
Switzerland	334 000	275 000
United Kingdom	235 000	203 000
Total	4 500 000	4 500 000

The graph below illustrates Table 8. The annual contributions remain stable across Options B and C. Except for a few countries (with higher GDP/cap), choosing between the two options will not greatly impact the budgets of the DiSSCo future members.

Figure 9: visualisation of annual membership fees distribution according to the two proposals selected

CHAPTER 5: Potential future developments of the DiSSCo RI business model

5.1 DiSSCo Business Framework

The DiSSCo RI can be represented with concentric circles. At the centre there is the hub which coordinates the demand and the provision of services. Around this hub, there is the perimeter of the ERIC: it can encompass bodies other than the hub. Service Level Agreements (SLAs) may be signed with institutions who would then become service providers on behalf of the ERIC. The final circle is the Research Infrastructure: inside this circle are the institutions who implement the activities of the RI that are already part of the institutions' missions. The addition of all the concentric circles represents the economic value and, at the same time, the economic impact of the RI and thus – for DiSSCo – the economic impact of digitisation of natural science collections in Europe.

DiSSCo RI's peculiarity is that it is intended to be mainly virtual and work with a distributed architecture that impacts the costs of the RI:

- i) The costs to coordinate the RI and provide some of its core services are fixed and mainly centralised.
- ii) The costs for the nodes / members to provide services on demand on behalf of the RI are variable and mainly decentralised.

It is important to make the distinction between the ERIC costs and the costs of the RI.

- The ERIC costs can be considered as fixed and centralised: the cost to run the Central Hub and provide the core services of the RI.
- The RI costs are larger and involve in-kind contributions from its members.

The RI itself can be broadly defined as provisioning access to natural science collections in Europe. The costs to provide this access can be extensively large: from travelling to the field in order to collect new specimens, to digitising collections and preserving the collections in the long-term. This is mainly the responsibility of DiSSCo members, and the role of the ERIC will be to ease the connection between the demand for access and access providers.

This objective can be met by designing e-services: IT tools should make the data FAIR and facilitate the production of data related to natural science collections. With that understanding, the core service of the ERIC will be to design and maintain these digital services.

In a broader perspective, the funding of an ERIC is not limited to its Member States. DPP WP4 also studies the opportunities to charge for some DiSSCo services (T4.2). Here, the goal is to understand who are the potential users of the RI and what is the market of the research infrastructure. This work relates to cost calculation: the pricing of the services should not fall below the actual cost to provide

the services. According to the findings of this task, a model for charging services could be developed. However, the determinant question in the elaboration of this model asks which users would be required to pay for the services. Specifically, will users whose research is publicly funded pay for these services? This question links to task 4.3: institutions/researchers could have free access to the RI services as their country would participate in its funding. Meanwhile, users from countries other than the Member States might be required to pay in order to access the services.

Another option for funding the activities of the ERIC concerns EU funding opportunities. As DiSSCo will mainly provide services for research-related activities, it can apply to the Horizon Europe programme. Still, the ERIC should not limit itself to funding for research. Depending on its activities, the ERIC could apply to other types of EU funding.

5.2 Inspiration from other RIs: a growth model

In order to gain a more qualitative understanding of the funding models of research infrastructures, WP4 met with representatives of ELIXIR and BBMRI. ELIXIR is not an ERIC but an international organisation. It has a similar functioning to DiSSCo: a Central Hub and a network of institutions that implement part of the services of the RI. BBMRI is an ERIC whose statutes have been signed in 2013. Both RIs do not come from the same field as DiSSCo (environment) but can be inspiring in their mode of operation.

Results of the ELIXIR interview

ELIXIR explained that its Central Hub focuses on the coordination and administration of activities. It provides advice on standards and systems to be used within the RI. Within this framework, the Central Hub does not produce any technical or scientific services. An important element for the Central Hub team is to have the capacity (in this case 1 FTE) to monitor the impact of actions implemented by the RI. This makes it possible to justify the RI's expenditure and to have a more solid argument with funders about the place occupied by the RI and the impact of its services. The study of impacts can be done through KPIs, but also through qualitative studies and success stories.

Since ELIXIR was launched in 2013, the Central Hub has grown rapidly. Part of it depends on structural funding (member states) and part on project funding. ELIXIR's strategy was initially to have a strong hub to stabilise the activity and ensure coherence. Activities were gradually decentralised between the Hub and local nodes. Calls for projects were opened to select service providers. The hub allocates funding to the nodes to hire staff to work for the RI. The decentralisation of activities is done in stages with a smaller budget at the beginning to test the viability of their offer.

Results of the BBMRI interview

According to the BBMRI representative, the Central Hub should have the task of providing essential activities for ERIC funding, such as funding and coordination of activities. Again, a Central Hub ensures the coherence of activities implemented by the RI. BBMRI is in contact with 3 levels of partners: nodes, biological databanks and the public. Each member has to nominate a node to represent it.

BBMRI has also grown significantly: in the first year the hub consisted of 8 people, today – in May 2022 - it has 20. According to its representative, the DG's role is to visit European governments to convince them of the usefulness of the IR and to increase the number of member states. There are rarely more than 10 member-states at the start of an ERIC. The initial budget was around 1.5 million euros and covered mainly administration, technical teams (lawyers/IT).

5.3 Growth opportunities for DiSSCo: service provision and integration of member institutions

DiSSCo will be a distributed research infrastructure. This means that its actions will be distributed among its member institutions. The connection between the partners are the Natural Science Collections and the affiliated services. In this context, and mirroring the other RIs encountered, the question arises of the articulation between the Research Infrastructure and its members and the management of funding. It is also important to understand that the national nodes are the contact points between potential funders and the research infrastructure.

Results from workshops and questionnaires with DiSSCo national node representatives

In this context, workshops were held with the nodes to understand the expectations of national funders and the potential for distribution of DiSSCo activities to its members. Questionnaires accompanied these working groups. Of the 21 countries that have signed the DiSSCo Memorandum of Understanding and the 11 that participate in the DiSSCo Funders Forum, only a small group participated in this study. A first result is that 5 out of the 7 institutions that responded indicated that they are in discussion with their ministry on DiSSCo ERIC funding.⁹

According to the participants, the arguments that speak most to funders are the acceleration of the national research strategy and the establishment of links with existing research infrastructures. According to the institutions that participated in the study, the biggest risks for DiSSCo and its future funding is an uncertain political environment. A number of the participants in the survey were unaware of the funding of ERICs in their countries. According to the questionnaire's participants, one of the main added values of ERICs is to provide services that are not available elsewhere.

Another question concerned the allocation of funding to ERICs. In some cases, it is possible that they are allocated to the national node, which in turn transfers these funds to the central node. In another scenario, the ministry in charge of funding could transfer the contribution directly to the ERIC. According to the questionnaire participants, two of them indicated that the funding was transferred through the national node and one said that it was transferred directly to the Central Hub.

Another issue raised by the workshop series was that of digitisation plans driven by the European level. One of the questions asked whether other institutions involved in the project have implemented mass digitisation plans. From the experience of the MNHN, there are two types of digitisation plans. Some

⁹ The results of the workshops are more specifically studied within deliverable 4.3: Guiraud M., (et al.). 2021 Deliverable report D4.5 "Models for government funding".

are centralised at the level of an institution. Others are national: they are coordinated by a designated institution and implemented at the national level. This framework is inspired by the experience of the MNHN.

Between 2010 and 2012, the Museum implemented a project of approximately 11.2 million euros to digitise the entire herbarium of the Museum, comprising 6 million specimens. A year later, in 2013, the e-Recolnat programme received 16 million euros from the French research agency. This funded a digitisation project within a consortium of 9 partners in France. The project was implemented until 2019 and involved 34 institutions: 3.8 million digitised specimens and 162,400 palaeontological and zoological specimens were digitised.

Using this experience as an example during the workshops, 11 institutions responded to a questionnaire on national funding for digitisation programmes. Among them, at least 6 institutions have received funding for institutional digitisation programmes, including at least one for a nationally coordinated programme. This shows that digitisation programmes exist in Europe, that States can fund ERICs, and that the challenge for them is to have added value through unique services at European level.

This series of workshops raised the question of the relationship between the national nodes and the ERIC. Through the question of funding, the question of the distribution of activities and services within the infrastructure was raised. From this perspective, these workshops provided an opportunity to discuss the degree of integration of national and local nodes into the research infrastructure and the distribution of decision-making powers within it. Indeed, through this process, 3 different levels of contribution model were identified.

Basic model: fixed funds covers fixed expenditure

The first model is simple and relies mainly on contributions from the Member States. It finances the operation of the Central Hub - mainly coordination - and the provision of digital services. This has the advantage of containing much of the decision making in the hub which provides tools for the member institutions to provide their data. At the same time, it limits the action and thus the added value of the infrastructure, it guarantees the provision of a minimum of services and does not require additional agreements with the nodes to provide additional services on behalf of the infrastructure. In this framework, if users request access to collections, without direct funding to institutions, then the prioritisation of requests would be at the discretion of the institution. It would have no obligation to the RI as its usual funding is linked to commitments with their national funders. Without additional funding from DiSSCo, the quality of services provided by its members under the RI would therefore depend on the alignment between the institution's strategy and the RI's strategy.

Mass digitisation programme model

The second model adds a layer of complexity to the first model. The basis remains the same: national contributions finance the operation of the Central Hub and the digital services. In addition to this model, digitisation programmes can be imagined. These would be derived from a centralised strategy, potentially with types of collections designated as priorities for digitisation. These programmes would

be implemented within a number of RI member institutions. The funding arrangements are still to be clarified. In this hypothesis, the ERIC would benefit from centralised funding which would then be distributed among its members in proportion to the number of digitised collections. It is possible to imagine different alternatives for implementation, such as digitisation centres spread across Europe. The investments would then be supported by the ERIC. The institutions would have to transport the collections to be digitised to the regional centres. Another option would be for the institutions to organise digitisation within their own institutions. In this case, they would also receive funding from the ERIC to provide a service on behalf of the ERIC.

In terms of funding, income for digitisation programmes could come from the European Union. One can imagine European regional development funding (ERDF) might be used for the digitisation centres and European Social Funding (ESF) for training the staff who will implement it. The DiSSCo ERIC could lead the consortium and coordinate the response to the call for projects. As such, it would also be responsible for monitoring the allocation of funding and the progress of digitisation.

Under this hypothesis, the institutions could see their objectives and actions influenced by the research infrastructure, which would guide part of their missions. When this hypothesis was put forward during one of the workshops, the representatives of the national nodes expressed doubts about giving up some of their capacity to prioritise their actions. At this stage, the level of integration of the institutions in the research infrastructure is not defined and some concerns are expressed.

Example from ICEDIG: ERDF covers the implementation of a digitisation centre in Finland

A national centre of digitization expertise in Finland, Digitarium was launched in 2010 and operated until 2017, funded by a series of grants from the ESF. Totalling €M 2.1, this funding covered 70-80% of costs, with the remainder coming from the host city and the two participating universities. The funding was used to build the technological base for mass digitisation as well as human capacities. Additional funding of €M 2 was obtained from EU FP7 research projects, national RI projects, and commercial mass digitization services. This model of funding in eligible parts of Europe can be attractive for DiSSCo as a mean of establishing the needed digitization factories and centres of excellence. It is worth noting that the ESFRI Lifewatch RI is being largely built on a similar basis

Centres of excellence funding model

A third level of integration is added to this option, incorporating centres of excellence¹⁰. It is largely inspired by the functioning of other European research infrastructures, such as ELIXIR or BBMRI. In this hypothesis, the institutions holding Natural Science Collections would provide part of their tools for the benefit of the users of the research infrastructure. This model would be derived from the identification of institutional strengths: in the framework of DiSSCo Prepare WP8, a questionnaire was

¹⁰ Hardisty A, Saarenmaa H, Casino A, Dillen M, Gödderz K, Groom Q, Hardy H, Koureas D, Nieva de la Hidalga A, Paul DL, Runnel V, Vermeersch X, van Walsum M, Willemsse L (2020) Conceptual design blueprint for the DiSSCo digitization infrastructure - DELIVERABLE D8.1. Research Ideas and Outcomes 6: e54280. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e54280>

circulated to identify the areas in which DiSSCo member institutions have more expertise. One hypothesis is that, with the results of this work, it would be possible to designate institutions with certain facilities, a certain type of collection, as the reference within the RI to provide specific services. They would then be designated as a centre of excellence and included in the list of services provided by the RI.

In this case, the question arises of the contract that would bind the ERIC to the centres of excellence. At this stage, service level agreements are envisaged. They would describe the services provided by the centres on behalf of the RI. In the case of such contracts, they may include expected service levels: the institution must respond to the user in X time, provide a specific service with a specific quality level, etc. There is a constraining dimension which implies that in order to deliver this level of service, institutions will have to hire teams or change the priorities of existing teams to ensure that the contract is met. This has a cost for institutions, particularly if they are receiving funding where they are already committed to a certain level of service. In this light, if the RI expects a high level of service, it is conceivable that the SLAs could determine a financial commitment from the ERIC. It would describe the expectations on the services provided by the institution and in exchange they would receive funding.

This model would have the advantage of increasing the range of services offered by the RI and capitalising on the skills already developed by the RI members. Initial investments would be lower because some of the skills would already have been developed before the RI was built.

These three different scales of RI implementation have an impact on the level and number of services provided. Digitisation programmes increase the amount of data shared by the RI. Centres of excellence increase the services provided by the ERIC. However, this implies either a perfect strategic alignment between the DiSSCo ERIC's objectives and the objectives of its member-institutions, or finding additional funding to cover the additional expenses supported by the institutions to provide services on behalf of the ERIC.

Basic model: fixed funds cover fixed costs

Mass digitisation programme model: DiSSCo as a data producer

Centres of excellence funding model

Figure 10 - DiSSCo national contribution models

CHAPTER 6: Conclusions

ERICs are organisations designed by the EU to structure the European research ecosystem and to encourage large-scale, international, scientific projects. They are meant to provide services, notably thanks to a coordinated network who is able to provide access to different types of facilities and resources. Beyond serving a community, RIs allow multidisciplinary interactions through policies that aim to ease access to different scientific facilities and FAIR data.

On average, more than 80% of ERICs' funding comes from public sources. The most sustainable of these are from Member countries who signed the ERIC statutes and committed to annually funding the ERIC.

For DiSSCo, WP4 recommends that the contributions from its members should be proportional to their economic power, R&D spending and population size. These three indicators can rank countries via different factors that reflect their potential use of the RI and their economic capacity. Such indicators propose an equitable distribution of the contributions among its members. In order to ensure a balanced distribution of the costs among DiSSCo funders, the WP4 recommends to distribute the indicators selected either with 40% GDP and 60% GERD/cap or 60% GDP/cap and 40% GERD.

With this proposal, WP4 recommends that to be sustainably funded with the proposed contributions, DiSSCo needs a commitment from more than the minimum of three Members legally required to constitute an ERIC.

The annual membership fees shall provide an annual secured funding to the ERIC. Once the statutes are signed, the first objective of DiSSCo central hub will be to start the operation of the RI, including provision of services.

From that perspective, there are growth opportunities for RIs like DiSSCo. The first one is to progressively enlarge the Member countries by convincing them to commit to the RI. This would require commitment from the Director General who shall visit and convince potential members to join the ERIC. In addition, ERICs are eligible for EU funding. This kind of funds require complex and time-consuming preliminary work and they are connected to pre-requirements determined by the EU. If DiSSCo seeks to benefit from these funds, it needs to develop projects that correspond to EU strategic planning. The DiSSCo perimeter is notably eligible for Horizon Europe, Invest EU, Digital Europe Programme, the European Regional Development Fund, the Transnational Access Scheme and the advisory services from the European Investment Bank. In addition, there are some alternative sources of funding such as national funding: ERICs are eligible for these funds but they are not fully recognised and suffer from a lack of information at national level.

Finally, the more DiSSCo will grow and will gain in maturity, the more it will be able to enlarge its activities. When the time comes, the question of the distribution of its activities, and of its funding will be raised. As a distributed RI, it is essential that DiSSCo ERIC capitalizes on the knowledge of its member institutions and encourages the development of centres of excellence among them.

Appendix 1: introduction of X-Officio

X-officio provides legal, governance, procurement and management support to inter-governmental and national [research infrastructures](#), [ERICs](#), research facilities and laboratories used by the science community to conduct research and foster innovation.

X-officio supports departments of administration, COOs, DG/CEOs and national ministries in all matters pertaining to legal, governance, procurement and management in the process of establishing, constructing and operating a research infrastructure. They also support business and contractual partners in legal and procurement matters.¹¹

Expert for WP4: Markus Pasterk

Markus Pasterk is a molecular biologist by training and served as an executive in national and international organisations. He held the positions of Administrative Director at BBMRI ERIC, a Scientific Coordinator at IARC/ WHO (Lyon, France), Director General at the Austrian Science Ministry and COO/ VP at the International Prevention Research Institute.

Markus specialises in management of European research infrastructures, from business planning to strategy implementation, governance and operations. Since 2017 he is a visiting professor for management at the "Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures" (University of Milano- Bicocca) and prior to that he was a senior lecturer at Dundee University.

Markus was project coordinator of the H2020 RItrain project as well as WP leader in several other EU projects. He was also the coordinator of the successful proposal "ERIC Forum Implementation Project", while working for BBMRI ERIC.

¹¹ Text from X-Officio official website: <https://www.xofficio.eu/>

Appendix 2: explanation of the membership contribution

This annex lays out the mechanism of calculating the annual contributions by members, observers, and intergovernmental organisations. The overall amount of contribution shall be defined in the annual work programme and budget.

The following principles shall apply to contribution of members and observers:

1. Contributions shall be based on a combination of GERD/per capita and GDP [GERD and GDP/per capita].
2. The minimal threshold of a contribution shall be EUR 50,000 (for members).
3. Contribution of observers shall be calculated as 1/3 of the standard contribution for full members.
4. Contributions of intergovernmental organisations shall be subject to the General Assembly's decision and fixed on a case-by-case basis, taking into consideration the size of the organisation, its members, and the R&D capacity.
5. None of the Members shall pay more than 50% of the overall amount of contributions by members/observers. In case the contribution of a member exceeds this level, the difference shall then be distributed among the other member/observer states according to their percentage levels of GDP. This will be a monetary contribution (not in-kind).
6. The hosting country (statutory seat) shall pay an extra premium fee as defined by the formula.

The following formula shall apply to calculating the level of contributions:

DiSSCo general membership fee calculation model

For members:

$$DAM(x) = F * A(x)$$

For Host premium:

$$DAM(x) = F * A(x) + H$$

Whereas:

DAM: DiSSCo annual membership

F: baseline fee = 50,000 €

I: indicators = GERD/cap, GDP, [GDP/cap, GERD]

Cri: $[(10-1)/(maxI-mini)] * I(x) + [10 - ((10-1)/(maxI-mini))] * I(x)$

A: Contribution factor = CFa = $(1-\alpha) * CriGDP + \alpha CriR\&D/cap$ [CFa = $(1-\alpha) * CriGDP + \alpha CriR\&D$] x: country

H: Host premium fee calculation (25% of Central Hub Office annual costs)

Appendix 3: detailed data from EUROSTAT¹²

	Average GERD (M EUR)	Average GERD / cap (EUR / inhabitant)	Average GDP (M EUR)	Average GDP/cap (EUR/cap)	Average (Population on 1 January - total)
Austria	11 881	1 347	383 935	43 443	8 822 267
Belgium	13 379	1 173	461 249	40 350	11 398 589
Bulgaria	442	63	56 772	8 080	7 050 034
Croatia	509	124	52 716	12 873	4 105 493
Cyprus	136	157	21 721	24 940	864 236
Czechia	3 929	370	210 239	19 777	10 610 055
Denmark	8 905	1 541	302 221	52 177	5 781 190
Estonia	374	283	25 844	18 487	1 319 133
Finland	6 442	1 169	233 207	42 280	5 513 130
France	51 952	775	2 366 061	35 080	67 026 224
Germany	104 749	1 265	3 368 623	40 640	82 792 351
Greece	2 185	203	179 937	16 760	10 741 165
Hungary	1 961	201	136 535	13 967	9 778 371
Iceland	472	1 357	22 110	62 793	348 450
Ireland	3 970	820	327 033	67 200	4 830 392
Italy	25 095	416	1 768 211	29 533	60 483 973
Latvia	173	90	28 939	15 023	1 934 379
Lithuania	430	153	45 567	16 233	2 808 901
Luxembourg	721	1 197	60 221	98 850	602 005
Malta	74	154	12 981	26 673	475 701
Netherlands	16 798	978	775 063	44 963	17 181 084
Norway	7 600	1 435	361 782	68 100	5 295 619
Poland	5 966	157	499 094	12 993	37 972 964
Portugal	2 782	270	205 169	19 937	10 291 027
Romania	1 012	52	205 550	10 550	19 533 481
Slovakia	759	139	89 661	16 463	5 443 120
Slovenia	895	432	45 807	22 063	2 066 880
Spain	14 860	318	1 203 955	25 727	46 658 447
Sweden	15 976	1 580	475 856	46 793	10 120 242
Switzerland	19 752	2 328	633 491	74 400	8 484 130
United Kingdom	41 991	634	2 435 767	36 667	66 273 576

¹² Average figures between 2017, 2018 and 2019

Appendix 4: introduction to EU funding

One common characteristic of ERICs is their need for funding to support international and interdisciplinary projects and users, as well as their need of funding to sustainably develop their services and capacities. Thus, to permit the sustainable development of ERICs over the next decade, it is fundamental to have a good knowledge of the landscape of both EU- and non-EU funding sources.

Beyond ensuring funding for the development of ERICs, a good knowledge and optimal use of the funding instruments at several levels will also enhance the visibility of ERICs within the research community.

The sources used to generate this report are both presented throughout the text in their relevant sections and at the end of the document. This chapter will first introduce general principles of EU funding. In the second section, it will detail information on the different EU funding available for DiSSCo.

4.1 General information on EU funding

[Before you apply: EU funding for beginners | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

This section provides general information about types of funding for applicants interested applying for EU funding, that should be checked before looking for and applying for funding.

There are different types of funding: grants, financial instruments (loans, guarantees and equity), subsidies, trust funds, prizes and procurements (public contracts). The implementation rules for all types of funding are governed by the Financial Regulation.

4.1.1 Types of funding

4.1.1.1 Grants

Direct financial contributions from the European Union budget awarded by way of a donation to third party beneficiaries (usually non-profit-making organisations) engaged in activities that serve EU policies. Mostly subject to centralised management by the European Commission, either directly by its own departments or indirectly through EU agencies, executive agencies or national agencies.

Grants represent a major part of the European Union's expenditure and fall into two broad categories:

- i) Grants that finance actions intended to help to achieve an objective that forms part of an EU policy;
- ii) Operating grants that finance the operating expenditure of a body pursuing an aim of general European interest or an objective that forms part of an EU policy.

Grants are based on the costs actually incurred by the beneficiaries for carrying out the activities in question, and the results of the action remain the property of the beneficiaries.

4.1.1.2 Financial instruments

Measures of financial support provided on a complimentary basis from the budget in order to address specific policy objectives of the EU. Where appropriate, can be combined with grants.

Types of financial instruments include: equity and debt, loan guarantees and venture capital, capacity building, and risk sharing facilities.

Financial instruments can achieve:

- Financial leverage - multiplying scarce budgetary resources by attracting private and public funds to support EU policy objectives;
- Policy leverage - incentivising entrusted entities and financial intermediaries to pursue EU policy objectives through alignment of interest;
- Institutional leverage - benefiting from the expertise of the actors involved in the implementation chain.

These instruments, implemented in partnership with public and private institutions, address market failures in the provision of external financing and avoid any crowding-out of private financing.

4.1.1.3 Trust funds

Pool funding mechanism, in which several donors jointly finance an action on the basis of commonly agreed objectives and reporting formats. Each EU trust fund has its own governing board, which decides on the use of the pooled resources. An EU trust fund acts collectively on behalf of the EU and all the contributors to its financing. Information is available on existing [EU trust funds and allocation of funds](#).

4.1.1.4 Prizes

A [prize](#) is a financial contribution given as a reward following a contest.

4.1.1.5 Subsidies

Subsidies are a big part of the funding provided by the [European Agriculture Fund for Rural Development](#) (EAFRD), offering, among other things, direct cash payments to farmers so they can bolster their income. Subsidies also aim to reduce economic and social disparity in the EU's poorest regions. Through the EU's [Cohesion Fund](#), subsidies are awarded to help pay for infrastructure projects and protect the environment.

4.1.1.6 Public procurement contracts¹³

Purchase of services, supplies or works by a contracting authority (EU Institution or local administration in the Member State) via a public contract.

As a general rule, a public contract is clearly different from a grant:

- In the case of a contract, the contracting authority obtains a product or service it needs in return for payment;
- In the case of a grant it contributes either to a project carried out by an external organisation or direct to that organisation because its activities contribute to EU policy aims.

If you are looking for public procurement¹⁴ contracts, please see [tender opportunities](#).

4.1.2 Funding by management mode

All the programmes funded by the EU budget fall under one of three types of implementation modes¹⁵ depending on the nature of the funding concerned:

- **Direct management:** EU funding is managed directly by the European Commission;
- **Shared management:** the European Commission and national authorities jointly manage the funding;
- **Indirect management:** funding is managed by partner organisations or other authorities inside or outside the EU.

Therefore, while the EU provides the funding for a specific programme or project, it is not always directly involved in the day-to-day management. However, whereas the Member States are in charge of the implementation of the majority of the EU budget, it is the Commission that has the ultimate responsibility for its execution.

4.1.2.1 Direct management

In direct management, the European Commission is directly responsible for all steps in a programme's implementation:

- launching the calls for proposals
- evaluating submitted proposals
- signing grant agreements
- monitoring project implementation
- assessing the results
- making payments

¹³ French L, Livermore L, Alonso E, Casino A, Dusoulier F, Groom Q, Hardy H, Juslén A, Mergen P & Smith VS (2021) Procurement Strategy and Policy: DiSSCo Prepare WP 8 - Milestone 8.4, <https://know.dissco.eu/handle/item/504>

¹⁴ Pijls S. ; Leliaert F. ; Mergen P. ; Robertshaw S. Roadmap for the partnerships project within the EU PCP framework. DiSSCo Prepare WP 4, Milestone 4.4.

¹⁵ [Funding by management mode | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

These tasks are carried out by the Commission's departments, at its headquarters, in the EU delegations or through EU executive agencies (See section II); there are no third parties. Programmes implemented in direct management account for around 20% of the [EU budget 2021-2027](#).

Calls for proposals under direct management are published on the [Funding and Tenders Portal \(SEDIA\)](#).

[4.1.2.2 Shared management](#)

In shared management, both the European Commission and national authorities in Member States, such as ministries and public institutions, are in charge of running a particular programme. Around 70% of EU programmes are run this way.¹⁶

Example: a farmer with a project to start growing organic tomatoes should apply for funds under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) - and needs to go through the country's Ministry of Agriculture, or an equivalent institution, which would be in charge of managing the funds for the project on behalf of the EU. The Member States' administrations (at national, regional and local level) choose which projects to finance and take responsibility for day-to-day management.

[4.1.2.3 Indirect management](#)

Some funding programmes are partly or fully implemented with the support of entities, e.g. national authorities or international organisations. The majority of the EU budget allocated to humanitarian aid and international development is implemented under indirect management. Examples include the financial support to fight the Ebola outbreak in West Africa and the earthquake in Nepal in 2015. Programmes implemented under indirect management account for around 10% of the overall EU budget.

Under this management mode, the Commission delegates budget execution tasks to different types of implementing partners, for example:

- Third countries or the bodies they have designated;
- International organisations such as the [United Nations \(UN\) family](#), the [World bank](#), the [International Monetary Fund \(IMF\)](#);
- the [European Investment Bank \(EIB\)](#) and the [European Investment Fund \(EIF\)](#);
- [Decentralised agencies](#) such as the [European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control \(ECDC\)](#), the [European Food Safety Authority \(EFSA\)](#) or the [European Border and Coast Guard Agency \(Frontex\)](#);
- Public-private partnerships, including Joint Undertakings such as [Initiative on Innovative Medicines](#), [Shift2Rail](#), [European High Performance Computing \(EuroHPC\)](#);
- Member States Bodies such as [Erasmus+ national agencies](#), Member States' development agencies, National Promotional Bank.

¹⁶ National single portals: the single-entry points for EU funds managed by national and regional authorities.

4.1.3 Funding entries

These sub-programmes of the MFF can be accessed through different entry points, namely: Access by Headings or Spending categories; access by topics; access by National Single Portals; access by specific programmes; access by funds; and access by Agencies.

Figure 11 - Figure showing the sub-programmes of the MMF 2021-2027 that are relevant to DiSSCo and the different entries to these funding programmes, detailed in the following sections

4.1.3.1 MFF by headings

MFF headings represent the subdivision of the EU funds by different thematic. There are 7 headings altogether but only headings 4 to 7 are relevant to DiSSCo.

4.1.3.2 MFF funding by topics

[This page](#) lists information about calls for proposal (e.g. grants) **sorted according to the major EU topics and areas of action**. Information about other funding opportunities (e.g. public procurement) is also included on some of the pages. For some topics, both calls for proposal and calls for tender launched via different EU funding programmes are shown.

Areas of action include: **digitization, environment, infrastructures, education and training, research and innovation...**

For a full overview of funding opportunities per headings, consult section II.1.1. For more information on the different types of funding, see section I.1 and the [Before you apply](#) page.

4.2.1.3 MFF funding by National single portals – sorted by state members¹⁷

The national portals are websites set up by Member States to inform citizens about the implementation of Union funds in their countries during the [2021-2027 funding period](#). Each country has its own national website portal, which covers implementation of:

- [European Regional Development Fund \(ERDF\)](#)
- [European Social Fund Plus \(ESF+\)](#)
- [Cohesion Fund \(CF\)](#)
- [Just Transition Fund \(JTF\)](#)

National portals exist for the EU funds presented above – **these links lead to the same funding programmes as those presented in section 6.2.**

4.1.3.3 MFF funding by programmes or groups of funding

The management of these funds is done in collaboration with the European Commission and national public authorities. These portals constitute national single-entry points for EU funds, also providing access to all programmes in a country.

The national website portals and the programme websites offer up-to-date information on upcoming funding opportunities, namely which regions are covered by funding calls, who can apply, the amount of funding allocated to a call, programme and EU policy objectives, and timeline. These websites also offer useful information for applicants and beneficiaries whose projects have been selected for support. Success stories, highlighted projects, guidelines to apply to funding calls, information about training and other useful information is presented here (in national languages) and can serve as inspiration for aspiring project beneficiaries.

4.1.3.4 Funding through European Agencies

There are currently 76 European institutions and bodies that may represent potential partners for DiSSCo in the long-term. These agencies can provide advice, training, funding and other types of support to DiSSCo-ERIC and DiSSCo's users.

For example the European Environment Agency (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/>), or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA, [European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)) could represent potential partners for DiSSCo.

¹⁷ [National single portals | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

CINEA manages the programmes of the European Commission contributing to decarbonisation and sustainable growth. CINEA manages the following EU programmes, for which DiSSCo is eligible: Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), Horizon Europe, Innovation Fund, LIFE programme, EU Renewable Energy Financing Mechanism, Just Transition Mechanism.

4.2 Available EU funding sources and relevance for DiSSCo

This section presents the main streams through which the European Commission can provide funding and support to DiSSCo-ERIC, namely: the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027, the European Investment Bank and the Transnational Access Scheme.

These streams are subdivided into sub-programmes that are detailed in each section. Among the many sub-programmes included in the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027, the programme Horizon Europe may represent the main funding source for DiSSCo-ERIC; the sub-programmes of Horizon Europe are therefore presented in detail.

The current EU long-term budget, running from 2021 to 2027, is known as the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF). This budget is seconded by the instrument NextGenerationEU supporting the recovery plan for Europe. The MFF 2021-2027 includes the new EU budget structure, funding programmes, and data on spending and revenue.

The 2021-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework is divided into sub-programmes (e.g. Horizon Europe, Invest EU, Cohesion Europe...) that are detailed in the next sections.

Figure 12- Figure showing the four main streams through which the European Commission can provide funding and support to DiSSCo-ERIC. These four streams are presented in detail in the following five sections.

This section provides an overview of the funding opportunities financed by the 2021-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework and NextGenerationEU by heading. See also the new brochure on the MFF 2021-2027 and NextGenerationEU.¹⁸

Figure 13 - architecture of the MFF and its funding programmes. Information includes: stars classification depending of the relevance of the programmes for DiSSCo, potential recipients of the funding within DiSSCo, and other parameters.

¹⁸ Weblink: [EU funding programmes | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-commission.europa.eu)

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Horizon Europe: Research infrastructures²⁰

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for different levels of DiSSCo, depending of the calls, HE can be for central hub, national or local nodes, and users.

Funding opportunities for RIs include:

- Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (**INFRADEV**) - [Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership \(INFRADEV\) \(europa.eu\)](#).²¹
- Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem (**INFRAEOSC**) - [Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem \(INFRAEOSC\) \(europa.eu\)](#)²²
- Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods and advanced digital solutions (**INFRATECH**) - [Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods and advanced digital solutions \(INFRATECH\) \(europa.eu\)](#)

The aim is to enable new discoveries and keep Europe's research infrastructures at the highest level of excellence.

- Develop and fund transnational users' access to European Research Infrastructure's services (**INFRA SERV**)
- To provide users of RIs with research services, particularly in some priority domains: health, green transition, knowledge. E.g.: *"Research infrastructures services advancing frontier knowledge (Geosphere / Biosphere / particle and nuclear physics"*²³²⁴

²⁰ Weblink: [Horizon Europe: Research infrastructures \(europa.eu\)](#)

²¹ Related calls on the funding and tenders portal: [Search Funding & Tenders \(europa.eu\)](#)

²² Related calls on the funding and tenders portal: [Search Funding & Tenders \(europa.eu\)](#)

²³ Related calls on the funding and tenders portal: [Search Funding & Tenders \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁴ Weblink to EU research infrastructure programme 2021-22 with details on the funding programmes above : [wp-3-research-infrastructures_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

*Horizon Europe : Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions*²⁵

Funds research and innovation projects to boost top researchers' careers through mobility and innovative doctoral and postdoctoral training. Application via the funding and tenders website.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for DiSSCo's users and national and local nodes.

Who can apply for MSCA:

- **Postdoctoral Fellowships (PF):** individual researchers together with their host organisations. Find out more about [PFs](#).
- **Doctoral Networks (DN) and Staff Exchanges (SE):** international networks of organisations from the academic and non-academic sectors. Find out more about [DNs](#) and [SEs](#).
- **Co-funding of regional, national and international programmes (COFUND):** organisations funding or managing doctoral or postdoctoral programmes. Find out more about [COFUND](#).
- **MSCA and Citizens (formerly European Researchers' Night):** any organisation able to organise a public event to promote science and research. Find out more about [MSCA and Citizens](#).

*Horizon Europe: Reforming and enhancing the EU research and innovation system*²⁶

Aims at training researchers for successful participation in R&I activities while enhancing networking, gender equality, ethics and integrity.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for DiSSCo's national and local nodes, maybe users.

Who should apply:

- Universities, research centres
- NGOs, governmental organisations, civilian volunteer organisations, civil society organisations
- Citizens associations

Every consortium must assign a project coordinator who will be the main contact for the European Research Executive Agency throughout the project.²⁷

*Horizon Europe: Widening participation and spreading excellence*²⁸

Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence actions under Horizon Europe contribute to building research and innovation capacity for countries lagging behind. They will strengthen their potential for

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for DiSSCo's national and local nodes located in widening countries listed at the bottom of this section.

²⁵ Weblink: [Horizon Europe: Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁶ Weblink: [Horizon Europe: Reforming and enhancing the European R&I system \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁷ Related calls on the funding and tenders portal: [Search Funding & Tenders \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁸ Weblink: [Horizon Europe: Widening participation and spreading excellence \(europa.eu\)](#)

Areas of intervention:

- **Teaming:** Support/create **centres of excellences** as role models to stimulate excellence, new investments and reforms of national research and innovation systems.
- **Twinning:** Develop excellence in chosen research and innovation domain, increase visibility of the research institutions and universities, and upskill its staff.
- **ERA Chairs**, to support universities or research organisations from eligible countries to attract and maintain high quality human resources and help excellent scientists and their teams to become game changers in their field.
- **European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST)**, a cross-border scientific network helping excellent researchers and innovators get access to the European and international networks.

Who should apply: all organisations eligible in Horizon Europe can participate in Widening actions but only organisations based in Widening countries can participate as coordinators. Widening countries²⁹ are countries with low participation rates in FP7 and H2020 projects.³⁰

*Horizon Europe: Clusters - Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness*³¹

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for different levels of DiSSCo depending of the clusters and calls within the clusters.

Horizon Europe includes 6 clusters in its ***Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness pillar:***

- [Health](#)
- [Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society](#)
- [Civil Security for Society](#)
- [Digital, Industry and Space](#)
- [Climate, Energy and Mobility](#)
- [Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment](#)

Who should apply:

- **Universities, research institutes, research centres**
- Local, regional and national public administrations
- **Museums**, cultural institutions and the cultural tourism industry
- SMEs in the field of digital technologies such as augmented reality and virtual reality
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) active in the field of migration and radicalisation

²⁹ Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia.

³⁰ Applications on the funding and tenders portal: [Funding & tenders \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eas/eas-portal/)

³¹ Weblink: [Horizon Europe \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eas/eas-portal/)

*Horizon Europe: Co-funded European Public-Public Partnerships*³²

Co-funded European Partnerships are implemented in Horizon Europe as *Programme Cofund Actions*. These partnerships are involving EU countries, with research funders and other public authorities at the core of the consortium, thus favouring public-public partnerships. The former equivalents of Co-fund under Horizon 2020 were ERA-Net and the European joint programme (EJP).

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo's users and Member State's institutions.

Co-funded European Partnerships are based on a grant agreement between the Commission and a consortium of partners. The grant agreement is signed following a call for proposals for a programme co-fund action in the work programme of Horizon Europe (see also section on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions). Enabling public-public partnerships, this co-funding instrument supports cross-border countries and regions to link their research programmes with those of other member states and participate in joint activities.

Summary of the rules to be followed: [Summary of the Rules to be followed — ERA-LEARN](#)

Webpage to practical hints to prepare a proposal for Co-funded Partnership: [Preparing a proposal for a Co-funded European Partnership — ERA-LEARN](#)

Possible Activities to be funded include: Networking and coordination; research; innovation; pilot actions; innovation and market deployment; training and mobility; awareness raising and communication; dissemination and exploitation. It may also provide financial support, such as grants, prizes and procurement, as well as Horizon Europe blended finance or a combination thereof.

Limitation: A limitation can arise from the national rules of the Member's states, since some are in contradiction with ERICs mechanisms (e.g.: Co-fund may require that research is done in specific institutions that get the funding).

The European Commission also supports and provides guidance for public-private partnerships that are presented in section 6.2 Public-private partnerships.

³² **Weblink:** [Co-funded European Partnerships — ERA-LEARN](#)

*European Research Council*³³

Objective: ERC is the premier European funding organisation for excellent frontier research. It funds creative researchers of any nationality and age, to run projects based across Europe.

Relevance for DiSSCo: ERC hosts a dedicated portal for researchers. Applications would be by DiSSCo's users. Awards can be used by researchers to finance access to DiSSCo's facilities and services. DiSSCo's national and local nodes and member's institutions could serve as host for the award.

The ERC offers 4 main grant schemes: i) Starting Grants, ii) Consolidator Grants, iii) Advanced Grants and iv) Synergy Grants.

The ERC is led by an independent governing body, the Scientific Council. The overall ERC budget from 2021 to 2027 is more than €16 billion, as part of the Horizon Europe scheme. **Research grants provided by the ERC can be used to finance access to ERICs' facilities and services, but it requires ERICs to be eligible as large access facilities**, as well as that ERICs improve their visibility among the research community to attract researchers to apply to ERC with an ERIC as a host/partner, since many researchers are unaware of the existing ERICs and the services they provide.

Limitation: A weakness of this source of funding for ERICs concerns distributed ERICs that have faced administrative challenges when there is a simultaneous implication in the project of an ERICs headquarter (coordination/core team/Central Hub) and one or more of its national nodes. This adds significant hurdles to the execution of the projects and also has an impact on ERICs visibility as a single entity.

Grant applications portal: [Apply for a grant | ERC \(europa.eu\)](#)

³³ **Homepage:** [ERC at a glance | ERC \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.1.2 European Strategic Investments

The European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI) / InvestEU³⁴

Objective: The EFSI aims to overcome the current investment gap in the European Union by mobilising private financing for strategic investments which the market cannot finance alone. It will support strategic investments in infrastructure as well as risk finance for SMEs. The EU will provide €21 billion in initial funding and the European Investment Bank's own resources (€5 billion). The fund will be set up within existing EIB Group structures, allowing it to start quickly and to benefit from the EIB's experience.

The EFSI will have two main focuses: **Infrastructure and Innovation (managed by the EIB)**, and SMEs (managed by the EIB and the EIF).

Eligibility: Projects eligible for financing,

- Must have high societal and economic value contributing to EU policy objective
- Must attract private capital by addressing market failures.
- Must come on top of existing EIB and EU financing possibilities.
- Must be economically and technically viable.
- Must be consistent with EU state aid rules.
- Some examples of key growth-enhancing areas being targeted by the EFSI are:
 - **Infrastructure (transport, energy, digital, environment, urban and social sectors)**
 - **Education and training**, health, R&D, ICT, **innovation**
 - Renewable energy and energy efficiency
 - Support to SMEs and mid-cap companies.

Contact for funding request: Anyone – not limited to Member States - can submit their request for financing to the EIB for Infrastructure and Innovation investments.

³⁴ **Homepage:** [The European Fund for Strategic Investments | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/euifund/euifund_en)

*InvestEU*³⁵

Objectives: the InvestEU Programme will boost innovation and job creation in Europe. It will provide and attract **long-term funding**. InvestEU will leverage substantial private and public funds that are protected through an EU budget guarantee. InvestEU will serve to carry out investments in **sustainable infrastructure, research and innovation, digitisation**, small and medium-sized enterprises and mid-caps; and social investment and skills, across the EU.

Relevance for DiSSCo: central hub, potentially national nodes, to build partnership between DiSSCo-ERIC and partners (Private companies, Banks, Financial institutions).

The programme will be structured around four 4 policy windows:

1. Sustainable infrastructure
2. **Research, innovation and digitisation**
3. SMEs
4. Social investment and skills

Types of funding: provides **guarantee** to support financing and investment operations and advisory support for the development of investable projects and access to financing.

How to apply for InvestEU financing: project promoters should apply directly to the European Investment Bank or to one of the Implementing partners, as soon as the InvestEU guarantee is available to them. This will be marked on the InvestEU website. SMEs and small mid-caps, microfinance and social enterprises may also apply through financial intermediaries of the implementing partners. Finance from the other Implementing Partners - national and regional promotional banks, or International Financial Institutions will be available thereafter.

Eligibility: Public and private investors and project promoters, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and mid-caps, **service providers** and recipients of microfinance.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

MFF heading: Single Market, Innovation and Digital;

Total budget 2021-2027: € 10.28 billion, of which € 6.07 billion under NextGenerationEU (current prices).

³⁵ European Commission Webpage : [InvestEU](#) Programme website: [Home \(europa.eu\)](#)

*Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)*³⁶

Objectives: to accelerate investments in Europe’s transport, energy and **digital infrastructure networks**. To support the twin green and **digital transitions**, by contributing to the ambitious infrastructure targets for the European Green Deal and the digital decade. CEF is a key EU funding instrument to promote growth, jobs and competitiveness through targeted infrastructure investment at European level. It supports the **development of high performing, sustainable and efficiently interconnected trans-European networks** in the fields of transport, energy and **digital services**.

CEF makes travel easier and more sustainable, it enhances Europe’s energy security while enabling wider use of renewables, and it facilitates cross-border interaction between public administrations, businesses and citizens.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA – see below) that manages the digital part of the Connecting Europe Facility. CEF is relevant to National and local nodes, and public-private partnership.

The CEF is divided into three sectors: transport, energy, digital.³⁷

CEF Digital – HaDEA, the digital part of the Connecting Europe Facility contributes to:

- Development of safe, secure and sustainable high-performance infrastructure including Gigabit and 5G networks;
- Increased capacity and resilience of **digital backbone infrastructures**;
- **Digitalisation**.

Types of funding: The programme provides financial support, primarily in the form of **grants**, with different co-financing rates depending on the project type, to three main sectors: transport, energy, and digital.

Eligibility: Industry, small and medium-sized enterprises, **research organisations**, other **public and private entities established in a Member State** or in a non-EU country associated with the programme, or created under EU law, and international organisations. In addition to grants, the CEF offers financial support to projects through innovative financial instruments such as guarantees and project bonds. These instruments create significant leverage in their use of EU budget and act as a catalyst to attract further funding from the private sector and other public sector actors.

How to apply/Calls for proposal: [Calls for proposals \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-operations/infographic-117444.pdf) ; The programme will primarily be implemented through direct management by executive agencies.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 20.73 billion (current prices)

³⁶ European Commission Webpage : [Connecting Europe Facility Programme website: About the Connecting Europe Facility \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-operations/infographic-117444.pdf)

³⁷ - The digital part of the Connecting Europe Facility is managed by the [Health and Digital Executive Agency \(HaDEA\) – Most relevant sector for DiSSCo.](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-operations/infographic-117444.pdf)

*Digital Europe Programme*³⁸

Objectives: to accelerate the recovery and drive the **EU's digital transformation**, to build the **EU's strategic digital capacities** and facilitate wide deployment of **digital technologies**, to be used by EU citizens, businesses and public administrations. The digital Europe programme supports the **strengthening of digital capacities** for high-performance computing, artificial intelligence and cybersecurity, along with **advanced digital skills** and accelerating the adoption and best use of **digital technologies**.

Relevance for DiSSCo: relevant at all levels of DiSSCo-ERIC, from central hub, to national and local nodes, and individual users. **Digital-EDIH** programme is specifically dedicated to the European Digital Innovation hubs.

Includes several work programmes such as: DIGITAL Europe - EDIH Work Programme 2021-2023 (.pdf), specifically dedicated to the European Digital Innovation Hubs

Types of funding: funding is disbursed in the form of **grants and procurements** directly managed by the Commission, under the direct management scheme, or under indirect management for the high-performance computing and cybersecurity actions, by the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking and the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre.

Eligibility: Public and private organisations, industry and SMEs, scientists and academics, universities, etc.

Calls for proposal: [Funding & tenders \(europa.eu\)](#) ; [European Digital Innovation Hubs | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

Programme duration: 2021-2027;

Total budget 2021-2027: € 7.59 billion (current prices)

³⁸ European Commission Webpage : [Digital Europe Programme](#) Programme website: [The Digital Europe Programme | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.2 Heading 2: Cohesion and Values

The main programmes under this spending category aim to strengthen the cohesion among EU Member States. In this way, they reduce disparities in EU regions, within and across Member States, and promote sustainable territorial development. In addition, through investment in young people, health and actions to protect EU's values, the programmes seek to make Europe more resilient to the various challenges that our continent is and will be facing in the future.

The **Recovery and Resilience Facility** and **REACT-EU**, the two main programmes under **NextGenerationEU**, are also included in this heading.

Associated group of funding: European structural and investment funds (ESIF)³⁹

ESIF is particularly dedicated and relevant to RIs. Over half of EU funding is channelled through the 5 European structural and investment funds (ESIF). They are jointly managed by the European Commission and the EU countries. The purpose of all these funds is to invest in job creation and a sustainable and healthy European economy and environment.

The ESIF mainly focus on 5 areas:

- research and innovation
- digital technologies
- supporting the low-carbon economy
- sustainable management of natural resources
- small businesses

The 4 European structural and investment funds that are relevant for DiSSCo are as follow:

European regional development fund (ERDF) – promotes balanced development in the different regions of the EU. [European regional development fund \(ERDF\)](#)

European social fund (ESF) - supports employment-related projects throughout Europe and invests in Europe's human capital – its workers, its young people and all those seeking a job. [European social fund \(ESF\)](#)

Cohesion fund (CF) – funds transport and environment projects in countries where the gross national income (GNI) per inhabitant is less than 90% of the EU average. In 2014-20, these included Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia. [Cohesion fund \(CF\)](#)

European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD) – focuses on resolving the particular challenges facing EU's rural areas. [European agricultural fund for rural development \(EAFRD\)](#).

³⁹ [European structural and investment funds | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.2.2 Regional development & Cohesion

European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)⁴⁰

Objectives: To strengthen economic, social and territorial cohesion in the European Union by reducing economic, social and territorial disparities between its regions and supporting the full integration of less-developed regions within the EU's internal market.

The European Regional Development Fund supports investment, in particular, in innovation and research, **the digital transition**, SMEs, the environment and the net-zero-carbon economy. It also addresses economic, environmental and social problems in urban areas, with a special focus on sustainable urban development. In addition, it supports cooperation activities between regions in different Member States (under European territorial cooperation goal (**Interreg**)).

Relevance for DiSSCo: ERDF allows for capital investment in ERICs, for building and equipment, for the construction and upgrading of facilities and in certain cases, to access the services proposed by ERICs. ERDF is relevant for branches of DiSSCo-ERIC at regional levels (e.g. local nodes), particularly in disadvantaged regions;

Most relevant to DiSSCo seems to be the programme Interreg-B (part of European Territorial Cooperation).

Specific funding possibilities for: Online training, research projects, new academic chairs, equipment and buildings.

European Territorial Cooperation - Interreg is a part of ERDF⁴¹:

Interreg supports cooperation and collaboration across regions and countries, to develop joint services and strengthen solidarity. Interreg provides funding for projects between Member States, their outermost regions, the EU acceding countries and the neighbourhood countries. Interreg will support cross-border mobility, and efforts to develop environmental protection, emergency services, skilled jobs and access to public services for the next EU generation.

There are several levels of cooperation within Interreg:

➤ **Interreg A - Cross-border cooperation**

European Cross-Border cooperation, known as Interreg A, supports cooperation between NUTS⁴² III regions from at least two different Member States lying directly on the borders or adjacent to them.

➤ **Interreg B - Transnational cooperation – seems the most relevant for DiSSCo**

⁴⁰ European Commission Webpage : [European Regional Development Fund \(ERDF\) Programme website: European Regional Development Fund - Regional Policy - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eu-observatory/erdf-programme-website/)

⁴¹ [Interreg : European Territorial Co-operation - Regional Policy - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eu-observatory/interreg-programme-website/)

⁴² [NUTS Maps - NUTS - Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics - Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg_10_10_1)

Transnational cooperation, known as Interreg B, allows for cooperation over larger transnational territories or around sea basins. It involves national, regional and local programme partners in Member States, but also in some programmes, non-EU countries (third countries such as Iceland or Lichtenstein), Enlargement and Neighbourhood partner countries, and the Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs), with a view to achieving a higher degree of territorial integration.

Like all Interreg programmes, it aims at promoting better cooperation across countries within designated regions to find efficient solutions to common territorial, economic and social challenges, which are too broad to be dealt with efficiently at a national level.

Interreg B supports a wide range of project investments related to innovation, **the green and digital transition**, accessibility, **digitalisation**, public sector innovation and interoperability etc.

Interreg B particularly contribute to achieve the following goals:

- **Innovation, especially networks of universities, research institutions, SMEs;**
- Environment and climate change, especially sustainable green and blue economy, water resources, flood management;
- **Digital connectivity** and sustainable transport;
- Sustainable regional development, especially in terms of education, labour markets and cooperation;
- **Cultural heritage** and sustainable tourism development;
- Capacity building and governance;
- People-to-people actions and engagement.

➤ **Interreg Strand C: Interregional Cooperation**

The interregional cooperation strand aims at boosting the effectiveness of cohesion policy by promoting exchange of experiences, innovative approaches and capacity building between regions

Types of funding: ERDF finances programmes in shared responsibility between the European Commission and national and regional authorities in Member States. The Member States' administrations choose which projects to finance and take responsibility for day-to-day management. Productive investments in enterprises, infrastructure and public policies across a range of topics; consultancy services and advice; studies. Funding is disbursed in the form of **grants, procurements and financial instruments**.

Eligibility: Regional public and private entities, with special attention paid to **disadvantaged regions and areas**, notably rural areas and areas suffering from natural or demographic handicaps and outermost regions; and, indirectly, EU citizens, public or private organisations, and businesses.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 226.05 billion (current prices)

Cohesion Fund (CF) ⁴³

Objectives: to strengthen the economic, social and territorial cohesion of the EU and its sustainable development by providing **support to Member States with a gross national income per inhabitant below 90 % of the EU average** (listed below).

Relevance for DiSSCo: relevant for national and local nodes in specific countries.

To strengthen the economic, social and territorial cohesion of the EU. The fund mainly contributes to investments in the field of **environment** and trans-European networks in the area of transport infrastructure made by public and regional authorities. The Cohesion Fund mainly focuses on capital-intensive environmental and transport investments. EU resources are predominantly used **to support investments through grants**.

Types of funding: the Cohesion Fund is delivered **through shared management**. The co-legislators establish the legal framework and the level of funding and determine the allocations by Member State and category of region. The Commission adopts the operational programmes and cooperates with Member States' administrations on the implementation. Funding is disbursed in the form of **grants, procurements and financial instruments**.

Eligibility: Public and regional authorities in the following Member States: Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia; and, indirectly, EU citizens, public organisations and businesses.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 48.03 billion (current prices), of which € 11.29 billion transferred to the Connecting Europe Facility

⁴³ **European Commission Webpage :** [Cohesion Fund \(CF\) Programme website: Cohesion Fund - Regional Policy - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.2.3 Investing in People, Social Cohesion & Values

*European Social Fund+ (ESF+)*⁴⁴

ESF+ is a combination of four funds: the European Social Fund (ESF), the Fund for European Aid to the most Deprived (FEAD), the Youth Employment Initiative and the European Programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI).

Objectives: the main instrument for investing in people, with the aim of building a more social and inclusive EU. Provide important contributions to the EU's employment, social, **education and skills policies**. As part of the cohesion policy, the ESF+ will also continue its mission to support economic, territorial and social cohesion in the EU – reducing disparities between Member States and regions.

Relevance for DiSSCo: relevant for DiSSCo's education and skills aspects, particularly for national and local nodes. ESF+ can be used to recruit technicians, staffs in human resources, and staff to support high-technology training on digitization that will be proposed by DiSSCo.

The ESF+ supports the following: social innovation; investments in young people to help them find a qualification and a good-quality job and improve their education, training and lifelong learning; **investments in capacity building** and transnational/cross-border cooperation to strengthen fair working conditions, foster equal labour-market opportunities and enhance labour mobility. Studies, actions and training aimed at investing in people, creating and protecting jobs, promoting social inclusion, fighting poverty, and **developing the skills needed for the digital and green transitions**.

ESF+ also includes: **ESF Social Innovation+**, which aims to facilitate the transfer and upscaling of innovative solutions to the societal challenges of today. Through supporting transnational cooperation, the initiative aims to expand best practices in fields including employment, **education, skills and social inclusion** across Europe.

Types of funding: support under the ESF+ is implemented under shared management and indirect management. Funding is disbursed in the form of grants, procurements and financial instruments.

Eligibility: EU public and private organisations, non-governmental organisations, EU citizens, young people and children, people from vulnerable groups, etc.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 99.26 billion (current prices)

⁴⁴ **European Commission Webpage :** [European Social Fund+](#) (ESF+) **Programme website:** [Home](#) | [European Social Fund Plus \(europa.eu\)](#)

European Commission Education Programme⁴⁵

Description: range of educational and training opportunities available throughout Europe for students of all ages, including information on studying abroad, vocational training, recognition of qualifications and skills. **This includes the ERASMUS programme.**

Relevance for DiSSCo: For DiSSCo's training in digitisation.

Funding programmes: Funding to projects and organisations in the form of a call for proposals. Funding is provided for a broad range of projects and programmes covering a wide range of areas including education. Funding is carried out through decentralised and centralised actions:

- decentralised actions are managed at national level by national agencies located in EU countries;
- centralised actions are managed at a European level by the European Commission.

National agencies⁴⁶ are separate from EU institutions. They are legal entities set up to perform specific technical and scientific tasks that help the European Commission carry out policies.

Funding opportunities exist in education and training in the form of the Erasmus+ programme, which is a funding scheme to support activities in education, training, youth and sport.⁴⁷

Erasmus+⁴⁸

Objectives: to promote learning mobility for individuals and groups, along with cooperation, quality, inclusion and equity, excellence, creativity and innovation. It promotes non-formal and informal learning mobility and active participation in education among young people.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for DiSSCo's national and local nodes and users.

Types of funding: The programme's activities are implemented through direct management and indirect management with the support of the Erasmus+ EU national agencies. Funding is disbursed in the form of **grants, prizes and procurements**.

Eligibility: Students, researchers and academics, universities and other organisations working in the field of higher education in the EU, and the partner countries. Erasmus+ projects are submitted and managed by participating organisations. If a project is selected, the applicant organisation becomes a beneficiary of an Erasmus+ grant. Beneficiaries sign a grant agreement which entitles them to receive financial support for the realisation of their project (grant agreements are not signed with individual participants). As a general rule, organisations participating in Erasmus+ projects must be established in an EU Member State or third country associated with the Programme. Some Actions are also open

⁴⁵ Homepage: [Education | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://education.ec.europa.eu/)

⁴⁶ Portal for national agencies: [National Agencies | Erasmus+ \(europa.eu\)](https://nationale-agencies.ec.europa.eu/)

⁴⁷ Portal for funding opportunities : [Funding List page | European Education Area \(europa.eu\)](https://funding.ec.europa.eu/)

⁴⁸ European Commission Webpage : [Erasmus+ Programme website: Home | Erasmus+ \(europa.eu\)](https://erasmus-programme.ec.europa.eu/)

to participating organisations from third countries not associated with the Programme, notably in the field of higher education, vocational education and training, and youth.

In general terms, **the programme is open to any organisation active in the fields of education, training, youth** or sport. Several Actions are also open to the participation of other players in the labour market

Calls for proposal: Search Funding & Tenders (europa.eu)

Application weblink: Opportunities for Erasmus+ | Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes (europa.eu)

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: EUR 24.57 billion + EUR 1.94 billion under MFFR Article 5.

*Creative Europe*⁴⁹

Objectives: to optimise the potential of Europe’s cultural and creative sectors by offering opportunities for operators to develop technologically and artistically through innovative trans-border initiatives. To exchange, co-produce and distribute European works and make them accessible to a wide and diverse audience.

Actions promoting excellence in the field of culture; projects aimed at developing innovative audiovisual content; support to the news media sector, fostering pluralism, cross-border collaboration and promotion of media literacy.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Relevant for DiSSCo’s national and local nodes that have cultural purpose: e.g. museums. Can represent opportunity for artists in residence to use DiSSCo collections for art.

Creative Europe includes 3 strands:

- **CULTURE strand:** encourages cooperation and exchanges among cultural organisations and artists within Europe and beyond. Creative Europe aims to: foster artistic creation and innovation, support the promotion and the distribution of European content across Europe and beyond, **help artists find creation and performance opportunities across borders**, stimulate the digital and environmental transition of the European Culture and Creative Sectors
- **MEDIA strand:** supports the European film and audio-visual industries to develop, distribute and promote European works, considering today’s digital environment.
- **CROSS-SECTORAL strand:** aims at reinforcing collaboration between different cultural and creative sectors. This is achieved for instance through policy cooperation, the services provided by the Creative Europe desks, and the Creative Innovation Lab.

Types of funding: The programme is **managed directly** by the Commission and the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (formerly the Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency). Funds are disbursed in the form of **grants, prizes and procurements**. The Creative Europe desks contribute to the programme’s implementation.

Eligibility: media, artists, cultural and creative organisations within the EU and beyond, the film and music industries and networks, etc.

Calls for proposal: Funding & tenders (europa.eu)

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: EUR 1.84 billion + EUR 0.69 billion under MFFR Article 5.

⁴⁹ European commission webpage: [Creative Europe](#) Programme website: [Creative Europe | Culture and Creativity \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.3 Heading 3: Natural Resources & Environment

Driver of sustainability: investing in sustainable agriculture and maritime sectors, alongside climate action, environmental protection, food security and rural development.

Part of the programmes under this spending category support Europe's farming, agricultural and fisheries sectors and seek to make them more competitive. Other programmes are dedicated exclusively to the EU's environmental and climate objectives.

4.2.3.1 Agriculture & Maritime Policy

*European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD)*⁵⁰

Objectives: To support the transition towards a fully sustainable agricultural sector and the development of vibrant rural areas. Rural Development Programmes consist of measures and projects that contribute to the EU-wide objectives of:

- improving the competitiveness of agriculture;
- encouraging sustainable management of natural resources and climate action;
- achieving a balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities.

Relevance for DiSSCo: Only relevant for DiSSCo's in the case of investment in rural areas. In this case, funding may be relevant to local nodes situated within these local areas.

The EAFRD provides assistance to farmers and inhabitants of rural areas to increase sustainability and competitiveness, including through the following: boosting the use of digital and technological tools; actions to improve the attractiveness of rural areas both for living and for job creation; support for innovation and diversification of on-farm activities; village revitalisation; protection of the environment and biodiversity; and actions aimed at restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry, with a positive impact on biodiversity, soil, water and air.

Types of funding: The EAFRD is primarily implemented under shared management with the Member States.

Eligibility: EU farmers and rural stakeholders

Calls for proposal: Funding & tenders (europa.eu)

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: EUR 87.44 billion (before transfers between the common agricultural policy pillars), + EUR 8.07 billion from NextGenerationEU.

⁵⁰ **European commission webpage:** [European agricultural fund for rural development \(EAFRD\) Programme website: CAP funds \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.3.2 Environment & Climate Action

*Programme for Environment and Climate Action (LIFE)*⁵¹

Objectives: To achieve the shift towards a sustainable, circular, energy-efficient, renewable-energy-based, climate-neutral and resilient economy; to protect, restore and improve the quality of the environment, including the air, water and soil; to halt and reverse biodiversity loss and to tackle the degradation of ecosystems.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo's central hub and National Nodes.

The LIFE programme's financial allocation is implemented through four sub-programmes: nature and biodiversity, circular economy and quality of life, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and clean energy transition.

The LIFE programme aims to:

- facilitate the shift towards a sustainable, circular, energy-efficient, renewable energy-based, climate-neutral and resilient economy
- protect, restore and improve the quality of the environment, including the air, water and soil
- halt and reverse biodiversity loss
- tackle the degradation of ecosystems

The financial envelope of the LIFE Programme is implemented via four sub-programmes:

- Nature and Biodiversity
- Circular Economy and Quality of Life
- Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation
- Clean Energy Transition

The programme supports demonstration, best practice, coordination and support actions, **capacity building**, and governance projects. This includes large scale Strategic Integrated Projects and Strategic **Nature projects**, which support the implementation of environmental and climate plans, as well as programmes and **strategies developed at regional, multi-regional or national level**.

Types of funding: The budget of the LIFE programme is implemented through direct management. Funding is disbursed in the form of grants, procurements and prizes.

Eligibility: EU national or local authorities, private commercial organisations and private non-commercial organisations (e.g. non-governmental organisations). Natural persons are not eligible to apply.

Calls for proposal: Search Funding & Tenders (europa.eu)

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 5.43 billion (current prices)

⁵¹ **European Commission Webpage:** [Programme for Environment and Climate Action \(LIFE\)](#) **Programme website:** [LIFE \(europa.eu\)](#)

*Just Transition Fund*⁵²

Objectives: the European Commission provides grants that are disbursed to the Member States in line with their territorial just transition plans. These plans identify the eligible territories, i.e. those expected to be the most impacted by the green transition. Actions aimed at economic diversification and reconversion of the territories concerned include: backing productive investments in SMEs, creation of new firms, research and innovation, environmental rehabilitation, clean energy projects, up- and reskilling of workers, job-search assistance and active inclusion of affected workers in jobseekers' programmes, as well as the transformation of existing carbon-intensive installations in cases where this transformation leads to substantial emission cuts and job protection.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo's central hub and National Nodes, DiSSCo must have partners in regions identified as negatively affected by the green transition

The Just Transition Fund supports the economic diversification and reconversion of the territories concerned. This means:

- investments in Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
- creation of new firms
- **research and innovation**
- environmental rehabilitation
- clean energy
- up- and reskilling of workers
- job-search assistance
- transformation of existing carbon-intensive installations

Types of funding: The budget is implemented through shared management. Funding is disbursed in the form of grants, procurements and financial instruments.

Eligibility: National and local authorities; businesses and start-ups in the regions where the magnitude and impact of the climate transition are greatest.

Programme duration: 2021-2027

Total budget 2021-2027: € 19.32 billion, of which € 10.87 billion under NGEU (current prices)

⁵² **European Commission Webpage:** [Just Transition Fund](#) **Programme website:** [Just Transition funding sources | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.4 European Investment Bank (EIB)⁵³

EIB description and services: EIB has equity to directly finance a panel of companies, institutions, SMEs, projects, etc. EIB offers different types of products and services, detailed below and available here: [What we offer \(eib.org\)](#) [Equity \(eib.org\)](#)

Relevance for DiSSCo: Advisory services are relevant financial products for DiSSCo. The programme **InnovFIN** is particularly relevant for RIs. Equity, guarantees, and loans are relevant financial instruments for DiSSCo.

Access to the services are restricted to the projects that are in concordance with EIB's priorities, that are listed below and also available at this website: [Our priorities \(eib.org\)](#)

Figure 14 -Screenshot of EIB priorities

4.2.4.1 Details on EIB products relevant to DiSSCo

Through member states and national agencies/ministries DiSSCo may benefit from advisory services⁵⁴ in 3 categories:

- **Strategic development:** to offer strategic support to help promoters and beneficiaries to realise their projects both inside the EU and worldwide
- **Market development:** to help clients define the parameters and specific needs of a sector, a region or a specific investment programme

⁵³ Homepage: [Homepage | European Investment Bank \(eib.org\)](#) EIB contact link to request financial support: [Contact us \(eib.org\)](#)

⁵⁴ Advisory services – [Advisory services \(eib.org\)](#) - Contact: [Advisory Hub \(eib.org\)](#)

- **Project development:** the EIB advisory services offers support preparing, structuring and implementing projects that are then funded by the EIB or by other financiers

Services are available for public and private project promoters, in order to support project development and public authorities, improve access to finance and the business environment in general. Services include market and sector studies, to understand the needs of various industries and regions, and help clients conceive their strategy and hone their skills. EIB's support also guides projects through the steps needed to secure financing, mobilising where necessary complex or ad-hoc financial solutions.

[4.2.4.2 EIB InnovFIN programme⁵⁵](#)

InnovFin Advisory support helps research and innovation (R&I) projects that face difficulties in securing finance, despite being fundamentally good projects. InnovFin Advisory guides its clients on how to structure their R&I projects in order to improve their access to finance. The service helps them to capitalise on their strong points and adjust elements such as their business model, governance, funding sources and funding structure to improve their access to finance. In the long run, this increases their chances of being implemented. InnovFin Advisory also provides advice to improve investment conditions through activities which are not project-specific. This includes things such as developing a business case for new financing mechanisms and preparing studies on increasing the effectiveness of financial instruments to address specific R&I needs.

Eligibility:

- Private sectors (large and small corporates, RDI clusters, industry associations, financial market associations etc.)
- **Public sector** (European Commission, Member States, government agencies etc.)
- Public-private and semi-public (**research institutes**, foundations, NGOs etc.)

Relevance for DiSSCo: Only advisory services are relevant for DiSSCo. Loans and guarantees products are allocated to states, government organisations, SMEs, financial institutions. Equity investing is dedicated to private & captive funds, or investment platforms sponsored by public sector.

To be eligible for InnovFin Advisory a project must: require a minimum €15 million of R&I investment; Fit the policy objectives of Horizon Europe; and not yet be mature for financing appraisal.

Contact for application: send request to innovfinadvisory@eib.org including a detailed description of the project, including business plan highlights and the expected budget commitment. The European Commission provides approval of eligible projects.

⁵⁵ **Homepage:** [InnovFin Advisory \(eib.org\)](https://www.eib.org/innovfin)

4.2.4.3 Financial instruments: equity, guarantees, and loans⁵⁶

EU funding is available through a range of financial instruments implemented in partnership with public and private institutions. Under NextGenerationEU the Commission will borrow on the capital markets on behalf of the EU.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo as an ERIC can request financial support to the European Investment Bank through different types of instruments that are listed below.

Types of financial instruments:

- equity and debt
- loan guarantees and venture capital
- capacity building and risk sharing facilities

For example, the EU provides loans to businesses of all types for investment in research and innovation. It also provides guarantees to help beneficiaries to obtain loans more easily or at better conditions from banks and other lenders. The EU may also financially participate in a project by owning parts of it. Financial instruments can also be combined with grants.

Financial instruments are implemented in partnership with public and private institutions such as banks, venture capitalists or angel investors. These financial institutions determine the exact financing conditions – the amount, duration, interest rates and fees.

Funding under shared management with Member States:

Financial instruments can be provided by the EU through financial intermediaries in Member States (shared management, **see section I.2.2**) to support its policies and programmes. Start-ups, micro companies, and larger businesses can all benefit from this type of funding.

Funding under partnership with the European Investment Bank:

The European Investment Bank offers loans, guarantees, equity investments and advisory services. Also called the “lending arm” of the European Union, it works closely with other EU institutions to support EU policies in over 140 countries around the world.

The EIB Group is also in charge of implementing 75% of the **InvestEU** programme (see section II.1.1.1.2). It will bring together, under one roof, the European Fund for Strategic Investments and 13 EU financial instruments currently available.

⁵⁶ **Homepage:** [Financial instruments: equity, guarantees, and loans | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/euipo/financial-instruments/equity-guarantees-and-loans/)

4.2.5 Transnational Access Scheme⁵⁷

Objectives: Transnational Access (TNA) programme enables scientists from various countries in Europe and beyond to use technological resources and expertise to enrich their projects with equipment and knowledge from specialised research sites/laboratories/observatories encompassed within ERICs.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo's central hub and users' projects: access costs, research costs, scientific and technological development, funding of central budget by state members.

TNA covers access costs and most research costs. Travel and accommodation costs are also eligible. TNA can fund scientific and technological development. **TNA is a true catalyst for ERIC Member State contribution to ERIC's central budgets.**

TNA constitutes an attractive alternative source of funding for ERICs and ERICs' users, especially TNA provides crucial supplementary funding for continuous sustainable development of ERICs (more services, access to new communities, etc).

TNA is essential for ERICs to provide services to the research community for little or no cost; it can support the early stages of service provision; it can become a stable instrument for sustainable transnational access for European researchers.

For ERICs that do not provide free access to their services, **TNA can fund ERIC's users to access their services**, in such a case TNA funding is allocated on selection basis and evaluation of scientific merit. TNA also promotes cross-RI mobility, the use of services by industry, and expansion of access to RI's services to other countries beyond the EU.

We also note that a joint approach of ERICs and funding bodies through TNA has the potential to boost ERIC's visibility and attractiveness for potential users.

With TNA, researchers and research teams across Europe have the opportunity to submit project proposals to be selected to perform experiments. Access is granted on the basis of proposals which are reviewed and evaluated by the TNA Committee.

The website [RICH | Rich 2020](#) is a European network of National Contact Points for Research Infrastructures that facilitates transnational and virtual access to Research Infrastructures.

Limitation: Member states of ERICs in development (without yet a common budget for the implementation of user projects) often experience a financial bottleneck with the Transnational Access Scheme.

⁵⁷ **European Commission Webpage:** [Access to European Research Infrastructures \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eu-ri/)

Appendix 5: overview, EU funding opportunities for DiSSCo

EU funding	Grants	Financial instruments	Trust funds	Prizes	Subsidies	Public procurement contracts	Direct management	Shared management	Indirect management	Central Hub eligible	National node eligible	Local node eligible	Users eligible	Relevance for DiSSCo
Horizon Europe														High
Horizon Europe: research infrastructure														High
Horizon Europe: Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions														Moderate
Horizon Europe: Reforming and enhancing the EU research and innovation system														High
Horizon Europe: Widening participation and spreading excellence														Low
Horizon Europe: Clusters - Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness														High
Horizon Europe: co-funded European Public-Public partnerships														High

EU funding	Grants	Financial instruments	Trust funds	Prizes	Subsidies	Public procurement contracts	Direct management	Shared management	Indirect management	Central Hub eligible	National node eligible	Local node eligible	Users eligible	Relevance for DiSSCo
European research council	Green												Blue	Low
InvestEU		Green					Blue			Blue	Blue			Moderate
Connecting Europe Facility	Green						Blue				Blue	Blue	Blue	High
Digital Europe programme	Green					Green	Blue			Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	High
European Regional Development fund	Green	Green				Green		Blue		Blue	Blue	Blue		Moderate
Cohesion fund	Green	Green				Green		Blue			Blue	Blue		Low
European Social Fund+	Green	Green				Green		Blue	Blue		Blue	Blue		Low
Erasmus +	Green			Green		Green	Blue		Blue		Blue	Blue	Blue	Low
Creative Europe	Green			Green		Green	Blue				Blue	Blue		Low
European agricultural fund for rural development								Blue			Blue	Blue		Low
Environment and climate action (LIFE)	Green			Green		Green	Blue			Blue	Blue	Blue		High
Just Transition Fund	Green	Green				Green		Blue		Blue	Blue			Low

Appendix 6: alternative and non-EU funding sources

According to the ESFRI white paper^{Ref7}, a joint effort combining European, national or other funding sources is vital for the healthy development of the pan-European Research Infrastructure ecosystem.

Figure 15 - Figure showing some possibilities for non-European sources of funding that may be relevant for DiSSCo. Details for each theme are presented in the outlined section of this report.

For ERICs to remain relevant throughout their entire lifecycle, scientific excellence is the condition *sine qua non*, which becomes, together with adequate human resources, crucial when it comes to long-term persistence in the operational phase. Effective governance and sustainable long-term funding (public and private) are other key elements for ensuring long-term sustainability of ERICs at every stage in their lifecycle.

There is therefore a need for ERICs to find alternative sources of income, to insure their sustainable development and functioning. Several operational ERICs are in the phase of developing a sustainability plan that consists of developing strategies and activities to support the long-term sustainability of the ERIC. The sustainability plan can include: implementation of user strategy (access fee and commissioned services), training, development of economic activities by the ERICs, and the interaction with the private sector and added value for society.

One of the ways to develop sustainability is to explore the diverse non-EU possible funding sources. This section of the report focuses on possible sources of non-EU funding that may be relevant for DiSSCo ERIC. **One of the advantages of non-EU sources of funding is that they rely on DiSSCo creating connections and having discussions with all partners of society, including local partners, that will strengthen the relationships between the ERIC and local/national communities.**

6.1 National and regional funding

Consultation of the ERICs legal statutes and *the legal framework for ERICs*^{Ref6} show that the main source of funding of ERICs is provided by the annual membership fees of the ERIC's Member States.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo-ERIC will be enabled to apply to national and regional funding schemes in the countries of its Member States.

An ERIC can also access public research & innovation funding bodies in each of its Member States.

The national and regional funding then come in coherence with, and in addition to, the Member State's contribution to the ERIC's central budget. Recognition and eligibility of ERICs for national and regional funding grants enhances their accessibility and boosts their attractiveness, therefore it is fundamental for ERICs to be eligible not only to the EU funding sources, but also to the national and regional funding which is available in member states in order to continue to broaden their services and supports. In return, ERICs will support national research by providing equipment, data, services and facilities to national universities and institutions, ultimately favouring a unification of research at the EU level.

Limitation: The lack of knowledge of ERICs statutes (whether they are international or national organisations) by EU member states is a weakness that challenges ERICs applications to national and regional funding bodies, for which they commonly have to prove their eligibility. A second limitation to the access of ERICs to national and regional funding is the fact that these funds will support the development of cross-border projects, implying that research funded by a country could be hosted in a different country, which can represent a barrier to successfully securing national funding. Therefore, there is a need for harmonised positioning of EU member states regarding the status of ERICs.

Types of funding: ERICs can access all national and regional funding streams within their member states. National and regional agencies can provide funding to ERICs, through cash or in-kind contributions (e.g. providing staff members).

An example of national funding to ERIC is from the EPOS-ERIC 2020 activity report: ***“The staff is guaranteed by three different funding sources, as illustrated in Table 2. First, according to the selected bid to host the legal seat of EPOS ERIC, personnel is seconded by INGV (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia) as the Italian in-kind contribution (IKC). The bid foresees the provision of INGV permanent staff seconded to EPOS ERIC (Italian IKC) for a total cost of €291,000 that is part of the total Italian Host Premium (corresponding to €1,023,000). Second, personnel are hired by INGV (temporary positions) using funds from the Italian Host Premium and provided in-kind to EPOS ERIC. Third, the ECO staff is also composed of personnel hired directly by EPOS ERIC. The human resource plan for 2020 foresaw the hiring of 5 people (5 FTEs).”***

Table 9 - Table from EPOS-ERIC 2020 annual report showing different financial sources for EPOS-ERIC

Name/N° people	Role / profile	Financial Sources	P/M year	Envisioned Costs (€)	Expenditure (€)
Massimo Cocco	Executive Director	EPOS-ERIC budget	12	170,000.00	170,053.00
8 people	ECO staff	Secondment: INGV in-kind personnel	55	240,800.00	246,674.12
4 people	ECO staff	Host Premium: in-kind personnel	24	88,194.29	85,973.55
2 people	EPOS ERIC personnel	EPOS ERIC budget	10	154,000	58,942.00

Weblink to regional and national funding authorities: [Managing authorities - Regional Policy - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

ERICs need to collaborate with academics and industries to insure their sustainable development. One possible outcome of ERICs accessing national funding is that it will enable possible partnerships between the public and private sector.

6.2 European Partnerships: Public-Private partnerships⁵⁸

European partnership is part of Horizon Europe, but it is presented here as an alternative source of funding because it has been designed to facilitate the connection with European private funders (e.g. industries) and to develop implementation of public-private partnerships.

Objective: European Partnerships bring the European Commission and private and/or public partners together to address some of Europe's most pressing challenges through concerted research and innovation initiatives. They are a key implementation tool of Horizon Europe, and contribute significantly to achieving the EU's political priorities.

By bringing private and public partners together, European Partnerships help to avoid the duplication of investments and contribute to reducing the fragmentation of the research and innovation landscape in the EU.

As stated in the ERIC forum policy brief 2022^{Ref5}, Industry and SMEs companies collaborate with ERICs as users, suppliers and co-creators, benefitting from the expertise, technology development and access to an unprecedented large network of researchers. Access to the ERIC's sophisticated expertise and instrumentation, usually at lower cost than through commercial services, particularly enhances the competitiveness of SMEs with limited capital funding. An ERIC may create an "Industry board" and employ a dedicated industry contact officer to support continuous engagement with Industry, organise joint events, increase visibility of the ERIC or support commercial users of ERIC's services.

6.2.1 Co-Programmed European Partnerships (2021 – 2030)

These are partnerships between the Commission and mostly private (and sometimes public) partners. The programme allows the Commission to work together with industry to boost investments in research and innovation and to overcome major climate and sustainability challenges, towards making Europe the first climate neutral economy. The partnerships will also deliver on the EU's digital ambitions for the next decade, Europe's Digital Decade, in line with the goals of the 'twin' green and digital transitions.

Relevance for DiSSCo: DiSSCo national and local nodes, digitalization centres. European Partnerships include an area specifically dedicated to digitalization (The European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies (KDT), presented below) to support the digital transformation of all sectors of the economy and society.

The implementation of Co-Programmed European Partnerships runs through the Horizon Europe work programmes and their calls for proposals. Each partnership provides the Commission with input on relevant call topics to be included in the work programmes. **The grants resulting from these calls are fully funded by Horizon Europe.** The private partners also develop additional activities, which are not funded through Horizon Europe, but which are included in the partnership's Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas.

⁵⁸ [Weblink: European Partnerships in Horizon Europe \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)

The funded activities typically focus on issues such as market deployment, skills development or regulatory aspects.

6.2.2 Co-funded European Partnerships using a programme co-fund action

These are partnerships involving EU countries, with research funders and other public authorities at the core of the consortium. They are presented in section III.2.6, Horizon Europe: Co-funded European Public-Public Partnerships.

6.2.3 Institutionalised European Partnerships

These are partnerships in the field of research and innovation between the Union, EU member states and/or industry. Institutionalised partnerships will only be implemented where other parts of the Horizon Europe programme, including other types of partnership, would not achieve the desired objectives or expected impacts.

Identifying partnerships: as part of Horizon Europe, the Commission identified 49 candidates for European partnerships, to ensure alignment with the programme's priorities. For institutionalised partnerships, the Commission has published inception impact assessments to see at an early stage if a partnership is feasible. These can be found following this weblink: [Have your say website](#).

Partnership candidates and contact details: The current list of candidate European Partnerships is found in Annex 7 of the [Orientations towards the first Strategic Plan for Horizon Europe](#). Results from the structured consultation of EU countries are summarised in the report on [European Partnerships under Horizon Europe: results of the structured consultation of Member States](#).

The partnership candidates are collected across 5 areas:

- health
- **digital, industry and space**
- climate, energy and mobility
- food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment
- partnerships across themes

Particularly relevant for DiSSCo is the European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies (KDT), as part of the digital, industry and space area ([Digital, industry and space \(europa.eu\)](#)), that is a programme dedicated to digitisation.

Additional details on European partnerships under Horizon Europe in the domain of Key Digital Technologies can be accessed with this document: [ec_rtd_he-partnerships-for-key-digital-technologies.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#).

Other public – private partnerships with relevance for DiSSCo could also include digitisation companies and automatic text companies.

6.3 International organisations

International organisations and non-governmental associations may represent partners or users of DiSSCo ERIC. This section provides hints and contacts to a non-exhaustive list of potentially relevant organisations that could benefit from DiSSCo's services and build a partnership with DiSSCo ERIC.

6.3.1 United Nations Organisation (UN)⁵⁹

The United Nations (UN) is an intergovernmental organisation whose mission is to ensure international peace and security, promote cordial relations between nations, promote international cooperation, and serve as a central focus for coordinating national efforts. It is the world's largest, most well-known, most widely represented, and most powerful intergovernmental organisation.

6.3.2 United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF)⁶⁰

UNICEF, or the United Nations Children's Fund, is a United Nations organisation that provides humanitarian and developmental aid to children around the world. With a presence in 192 countries and territories, the agency is one of the most well-known social welfare organisations in the world. Immunisation and disease prevention are among UNICEF's initiatives, as are HIV treatment for children and women, improving childhood and maternal nutrition, increasing sanitation, promoting education, and providing emergency relief in disasters.

6.3.3 World Health Organization (WHO)⁶¹

The World Health Organization (WHO) is a United Nations specialised organisation in charge of international public health. "The attainment by all peoples of the highest attainable degree of health," declares the WHO Constitution, which sets the agency's governance structure and ideals.

6.3.4 International Monetary Fund (IMF)⁶²

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) works to promote global monetary cooperation, secure financial stability, facilitate international trade, promote high employment and sustainable economic growth, and reduce poverty around the world while relying on the World Bank for resources on a periodic basis.

⁵⁹ Weblink: [United Nations | Peace, dignity and equality on a healthy planet](#)

⁶⁰ Weblink: [UNICEF](#)

⁶¹ Weblink: [World Health Organization \(WHO\)](#)

⁶² Weblink: [International Monetary Fund - Homepage \(imf.org\)](#)

6.3.5 World Bank⁶³

The World Bank is an international financial agency that lends and gives money to governments in low- and middle-income nations to fund capital projects. The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD) and the International Development Association (IDA) are the two institutions that make up the organisation.

6.3.6 United Nations Educational, Scientific & Cultural Organization (UNESCO)⁶⁴

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is a United Nations specialised agency charged with the duty of promoting world peace and security through international cooperation in education, science, and culture. It consists of 193-member states, 11 associate members and nongovernmental, intergovernmental, and corporate sector partners.

6.3.7 The Food and Agriculture Organization⁶⁵

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) is an international organisation that leads international efforts to defeat hunger and improve nutrition and food security. It helps governments and development agencies coordinate their activities to improve and develop agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and land and water resources. It also conducts research, provides technical assistance to projects, operates educational and training programmes, and collects data on agricultural output, production, and development.

6.3.8 World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)⁶⁶

The World-Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) is an international non-governmental organisation that seeks to preserve wilderness and reduce the human effects on the environment. With over five million supporters globally, WWF is the world's largest conservation organisation, working in over 100 countries and supporting around 3,000 conservation and environmental projects.

6.3.9 The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)⁶⁷

Free open access to biodiversity data. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.

⁶³ Weblink: World Bank Group - International Development, Poverty, & Sustainability

⁶⁴ Weblink: Accueil | UNESCO

⁶⁵ Weblink: Home | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (fao.org)

⁶⁶ Weblink: WWF - Endangered Species Conservation | World Wildlife Fund

⁶⁷ Weblink: GBIF

6.3.10 Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)⁶⁸

Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) is a not-for-profit, scientific and educational association formed to establish international collaboration among the creators, managers and users of biodiversity information and to promote the wider and more effective dissemination and sharing of knowledge about the world's heritage of biological organisms. TDWG is an open, bottom-up organisation. Anyone can become a member, individuals as well as institutions.

6.3.11 The Fair Digital Object initiative (Go FAIR)⁶⁹

GO FAIR is a bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative that aims to implement the FAIR data principles, making data **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable (**FAIR**). It offers an open and inclusive ecosystem for individuals, institutions and organisations working together through Implementation Networks.

6.3.12 European Open Science Cloud

In Europe, the United States, Australia and Africa, efforts to work towards an Internet of FAIR Data and Services (IFDS) are already under way. While keeping this global perspective, GO FAIR also contributes to the developments in the federated European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which can be seen as the European contribution to the Internet of FAIR Data and services; Europe's virtual environment for all researchers to access, store, manage, analyse and re-use data for research, innovation and educational purposes.

⁶⁸ Weblink: Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)

⁶⁹ Weblink: GO FAIR Initiative - GO FAIR (go-fair.org)

6.4 Foundations

There is a range of environmental and research foundations that DiSSCo could contact to request for funding, under the form of grants or sponsorship.

Some examples include:

6.4.1 Adessium Foundation (Netherlands): [Adessium Foundation](#)

Supports initiatives and organisations in the Netherlands and in Europe that are committed to an open and just society, healthy ecosystems and equal opportunities for everyone. The foundation is recognised as a public benefit organisation by the Dutch tax authorities.

6.4.2 Agropolis Fondation (France): [Agropolis Fondation - Pour la recherche agronomique et le développement \(agropolis-fondation.fr\)](#)

The foundation supports the agro-ecological transition, promotes partnerships to better understand and address the challenge of agro-ecological transition, re-imagine agriculture to ensure sustainable development. Agropolis gathers a network of 43 research units and 1600 researchers.

6.4.3 Children's Investment Fund Foundation (UK): [CIFF: Children's Investment Fund Foundation](#)

Independent philanthropic organisation to transform the lives of children and adolescents by providing grants in fields of education and climate change.

6.4.4 European Climate Foundation (Netherlands): [European Climate Foundation](#)

The European Climate Foundation (ECF) is a major philanthropic initiative working to help tackle the climate crisis by fostering the development of a net-zero emission society at the national, European, and global level. The ECF supports over 800 partner organisations to carry out activities that drive urgent and ambitious policy in support of the objectives of the Paris Agreement, contribute to the public debate on climate action, and help deliver a socially responsible transition to a net-zero economy and sustainable society in Europe and around the world.

6.4.5 King Baudouin Foundation (Belgium): [Heritage and culture | Koning Boudewijnstichting \(kbs-frb.be\)](#)

The King Baudouin foundation has several strands, including a heritage and culture strand with the goal to safeguard and preserve significant items of Belgian heritage for future generations and facilitate innovative projects with a local or international dimension, related to the natural, architectural, cultural or moveable heritage of Belgium.

6.5 Funding databases

There are multiple funding databases online that can be consulted to seek additional sources of funding, including, but not limited to:

Research connect: [About - ResearchConnect \(myresearchconnect.com\)](https://myresearchconnect.com)

ResearchConnect is a specialist research funding database built for and designed by the international research community.

GET.invest: [GET.invest – GET.invest is a European programme that mobilises investment in renewable energy in developing countries. \(get-invest.eu\)](https://get-invest.eu)

GET.invest is a European programme that mobilises investment in renewable energy in developing countries.

Catalyze: [Funding Database - Research & Development Grants - Catalyze \(catalyze-group.com\)](https://catalyze-group.com)

Guide to the most important research and development grants, worldwide.

Shared data: [Funding Database – Shared Data](#)

Compiling of funding opportunities.

Scientify RESEARCH: [Research Funding Database - scientifyRESEARCH](#)

To connect researchers with research funding information.

Appendix 7: recommendations from D4.3

N°	Description
1	All items of revenue and expenditure of an ERIC shall be included in estimates to be drawn up for each financial year and shall be shown in the budget (where revenues and expenditures shall be in balance).
2	Principles of sound financial management have to be implemented.
3	<p data-bbox="272 667 1139 701"><u>The key elements of an internal rules document on “financial rules” are:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="272 725 979 759">a. Framework: describe the ERIC in managerial summary; <li data-bbox="272 797 1386 869">b. Financial management principles: repeat those from the ERIC regulation, the Statutes and add others specific to your RI; <li data-bbox="272 907 568 940">c. Financial year dates; <li data-bbox="272 978 440 1012">d. Currency; <li data-bbox="272 1050 1386 1122">e. Request and dates for the annual contributions: when shall members pay their contribution, received in one or in several instalments and at which dates; <li data-bbox="272 1160 1350 1193">f. Interest rate to late contributions: how to deal with countries paying late or not at all; <li data-bbox="272 1232 1386 1265">g. Detailed formula for the mandatory annual contributions if not described in the statutes; <li data-bbox="272 1303 1386 1375">h. Rules to calculate membership fee for new members to join during the year: full membership fee or only parts, calculated from the month/quarter/half year; <li data-bbox="272 1413 1386 1485">i. Reference to statistical sources for the formula ingredients: put in all those references needed for the calculation of the membership share and how you use them; <li data-bbox="272 1523 1386 1594">j. Host country contribution/premium if not mentioned in the statutes: is it fixed by amount or percentage, how is it amended and/or evaluated; <li data-bbox="272 1632 1386 1733">k. Value and evaluation rules for in-kind contributions: in case in-kind contributions are available describe the process how they will be estimated or calculated and how they are evaluated and decided if their value will be included in the accounts; <li data-bbox="272 1771 1386 1843">l. How the draft budget is assembled and approved: who does what in preparing the budget and the contribution; <li data-bbox="272 1881 1386 1953">m. Accounting principles and rules: do you follow international accounting rules (IFRS) or if national, why; <li data-bbox="272 1991 1222 2024">n. Financial audits: how is the process of financial audits set up and by whom;

N°	Description
	<p>o. Principles of loans and bank overdrafts: who can draft loans and overdrafts approved by whom;</p> <p>p. Financial reporting: what shall be reported to whom and how; for a very good summary refer to the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Guidance document on accounting principles for ERICs;</p> <p>q. Duration of record keeping beyond the national rules: what are the national rules, and do you keep them longer?</p>
4	<p>Contribution rules should provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The method chosen shall be based on transparent, easy to acquire statistics and should make comparisons between countries possible; - a rule in case countries leave the ERIC; - The different countries' share should be calculated according to their population size, economic power, number of potential users, R&D spending or shall be equal for all. - Can have minimal and maximal thresholds in numbers as well as a maximal % for an individual country. - Include a specific rule/% for the host country premium; - May include an automated adjustment for inflation; - Special clauses for high volume infrastructure/equipment (not of interest for DiSSCo).
5	<p>For most countries, good statistics, both historically as well as current, are available from EUROSTAT, OECD.Stat and or World Bank Open Data</p>
6	<p>International organisations' participation can be directly discussed during a GA meeting and shall not specifically be mentioned in the Statutes.</p>
7	<p>No rule needs to be written in the statutes in order to guarantee a minimum level of funding for the ERIC.</p>
8	<p>It is not recommended to start the ERIC with less than 5 countries.</p>
9	<p>For observers, there is no rule but it should be detailed in the statutes. It is realistic to ask ¼ to 1/3 of the full membership fee. If observers have the same rights to access the service, 1/3 can be appropriate.</p>
10	<p>Regarding the amount of the expected in-kind contribution, this is to be included in the service level agreements (SLAs). It is possible to foresee with annexes an annual basis on the agreed monetary equivalent on which the annual commitment is defined.</p>
11	<p>Budget cycles should not be specifically mentioned in the Statutes. Each year the budget is drafted and if the GA agrees on it, it is accepted. In the case of higher investments, it is possible to prepare a two to three years budget with details and share it with GA.</p>

N°	Description
12	<p>A rule should be included in the statutes in order to clarify how it would work in the case a country joins the ERIC in the course of a year. There are two recommended options on that case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The country has to pay from the month it joins the ERIC to the end of the year; • If the country joins the ERIC after the mid-year, it shall pay for the full annual membership fee, if it joins the ERIC after the mid-year, it shall pay 50% of the annual membership fee. <p>In both cases, they commit their country for 5 years.</p> <p>Joining cannot be done on the date chosen but on the date after the GA or written procedure associated. It is very likely that the decision to welcome a new country will be taken during the GA.</p>
13	<p>It is not relevant to mention a financial penalty in case of early withdrawal in the statutes. There is already a rule in place in the case where a country leaves before the end of the first 5 years. A good option is to negotiate an early notification in case of leave.</p>
14	<p>There is no need to explain what the contributions will cover in the statutes. It is specified in the annual work programme attached with the annual budget. Both documents shall be approved by the General Assembly.</p>
15	<p>ERICs can obtain access to loans like any private company. The ERIC must demonstrate its bankability with the bank. The GA shall approve the loan. In the case of DiSSCo, the decision should be taken 10 years before the subscription to the loan.</p>
16	<p>Reserve authorisation will depend on the financial and monetary rules of the country with statutory seats. The rules will vary from one country to another. In some countries, ERICs are seen as a private organisation, therefore they should follow private financial rules. In others, they are seen as public institutions. Typically, in the European Union, public organisations are advised against establishing and keeping reserves. The same advice does not apply for the private sector.</p>
17	<p>Host premium shall cover 25% of the annual cost of the Central Hub Office.</p>
18	<p>Observers shall pay one third of full annual membership, based on the same factors as for members.</p>
19	<p>One Member State annual contribution shall not exceed 50% of total annual contributions to DiSSCo ERIC.</p>
20	<p>Use a specific consumer price index that has been developed within the EU: the harmonised index of consumer prices (HICP). One possibility is either a fixed percentage or a flexible one using the last years published. This would mean either choosing one of the incorporation states (as most goods and services would be covered there) or an average of participating states (which will need to be recalculated with each new member) or the EU average.</p>

N°	Description
21	In order to streamline the indicators selected, DiSSCo ERIC national contributions can be calculated on the average GDP, population and GERD over 3 years.
22	The baseline (F) is set at 50,000 € per year. It means that each DiSSCo Member State should pay at least that amount of money.
23	It is important to make the distinction between the ERIC costs and the costs of the RI. The ERIC costs can be considered as fixed and centralised: the cost to run the Central Hub and provide the core services of the RI. The RI costs are larger and involve in-kind contributions from its members. The RI itself can be broadly defined as provisioning access to natural science collections in Europe. The costs to provide this access can be extensively large: from travelling to the field in order to collect new specimens, to digitising collections and preserving the collections in the long-term. This is mainly the responsibility of DiSSCo members, and the role of the ERIC will be to ease the connection between the demand for access and access providers.
24	If users request access to collections, without direct funding to member-institutions, then the prioritisation of requests would be at the discretion of the institution. It would have no obligation to the RI as its usual funding is linked to commitments with their national funders. Without additional funding from DiSSCo, the quality of services provided by its members under the RI would therefore depend on the alignment between the institution's strategy and the RI's strategy.
25	In the case of EU funding grouped applications, DiSSCo ERIC could lead the consortium and coordinate the response to the call for projects. As such, it would also be responsible for monitoring the allocation of funding and the progress of digitisation.
26	With WP8 results on specialisation plans, it would be possible to designate institutions with certain facilities, a certain type of collection, as the reference within the RI to provide specific services. They would then be designated as a centre of excellence and included in the list of services provided by the RI.
27	If the RI expects a high level of service, it is conceivable that SLAs setting the rules between the ERIC and its member-institutions could contain a financial commitment from the ERIC. It would describe the expectations on the services provided by the institution and in exchange they would receive funding.
28	The most relevant funding sources for DiSSCo-ERIC are from the EU Multiannual Financial Framework: Horizon Europe, Invest EU, Digital Europe Programme, and the European Regional Development Fund. Horizon Europe and its sub-programmes will be particularly relevant for DiSSCo. Other potentially important sources of funding for DiSSCo-ERIC will include the services provided by the European Investment Bank, especially the programme InnovFIN that is

N°	Description
	particularly relevant for RIs, the advisory services that are financial products provided by the EIB that will be relevant for DiSSCo, and financial instruments equity, guarantees, and loans.
29	The Transnational Access Scheme is stated as a true catalyst for ERIC Member State contribution to ERIC's central budgets, that can become a stable instrument for sustainable development of the ERIC, although limitations of use are reported for member states of ERICs in development.
30	Among the non-EU sources, the national and regional sources of funding should really be explored in each member state, since they have the potential not-only to fund DiSSCo ERIC, but also to make DiSSCo ERIC more visible, more accessible and to durably settle DiSSCo's national and local nodes in the heart of the regions where they will be located.
31	Maximise the relationship between ERICs and stakeholders at the local, national and international levels is a recommendation of the EU to develop partnerships, particularly with the private sector.

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